

Chapter 1

Introduction: Putting Things in Perspective

In opening this thesis, I would like to firstly acknowledge the fact that for many Indonesians, both of the past and of today, the notion that Indonesia is something sacred, whose sacredness must be protected from any act of “sacrilege,” was and is quite strong. My acknowledgement is necessary here because, for these people, talking about Indonesia is comparable to talking a sensitive issue. Questioning Indonesia or any thing related to it, especially when you are an Indonesian, can easily be misinterpreted as an attitude of being unpatriotic, or non-nationalist, betraying the national inheritance and “history,” and so on and so forth. History textbooks being used in Indonesian schools have been constantly telling their students about millions of the heroic forefathers and foremothers who had unselfishly shed their sweats, bloods, and tears in the process of conceptualizing, materializing, and defending the newly born nation. Although this act of self-sacrifice is not in itself an atypical case of Indonesia as a postcolonial state that proclaimed its independence from their European and American colonizers in the aftermath of World War II, for many other states also have invented their own stories of national revolution (Anderson, 1991:3), the story of Indonesian nationalists’ heroism has been propagated in such a systematic way to young Indonesians so that anyone dares to question anything related to it can only mean one thing: he or she is not Indonesian enough. In short, what is

intended is that you will feel bad, scrupulous, and ungrateful for your critical attitude toward Indonesian nationalism.

Still, to many Indonesians, Indonesia is as “real” and physical as the national flag, the national soccer team, the president, etc. When anything related to those “real” and physical attributes of Indonesia is, for example, perceived to be threatened by the outside world or those seen as others, the sense of nationalism as a member of Indonesian community is once more aroused and getting stronger to prompt mobilization when necessary. This all suggests, following Benedict Anderson, how important being an Indonesian, or a member of Indonesia, is to many of its subjects as a mode of self-identification. And there is no sign that the majority of Indonesians will abandon it in the near future.

The quite strong sense of patriotism among many Indonesians, combined with Benedict Anderson’s idea about the nature of nationalism as an exclusionary mode of identity—referring to nationalism’s inherent feature of always trying to otherize others in order to make its own national identity somehow stronger—makes nationalism in general, and Indonesian nationalism in particular, prone to xenophobia. Xenophobia itself could broadly be defined as intense, irrational dislike or fear of people from other countries. The on-and-off tense relationship between Indonesia and its closest neighbor, Malaysia—a country often being seen as a potential, and sometimes real, threat to Indonesian’s political, social, and cultural “integrity”—is just one good example of how nationalism and “xenophobia” in its broader sense is not always easy to distinguish. In a case of

xenophobia, the emotional and irrational side of nationalism overcomes its rational side. And yet, despite that fact that nationalism can be at times irrational and illogical, we cannot simply ignore it since nationalism, as has been implied, is today—as it was half century ago—one of the most important and potent identifications in this modern world. The best we should do is to find the delicate balance that will put our attachment to the nation-state, or simply put our nationalism, in its rightful place, if there is one. The most appropriate attitude toward nationalism is, in my opinion, a critical understanding and constant valuation of what nationalism is, what nationalism wants, what nationalism promises, and a continuous reflection of how it serves humanity and why it was desired at the first place. My own personal hope is that as many as possible Indonesians have a better understanding of why they die for or what they self-identify with. My presumption is that so far how many Indonesians understand Indonesian nationalism, what they read about it, how they live their Indonesianess are somehow inadequate or, even worse, not quite right. In other words, it must be admitted that the idea about what Indonesia is and how it should be that many Indonesians learned at school—the idea about Indonesia that the regime or regimes want them to believe—is an interpretation in need of a critical revisit.

One common problem in making Indonesia a closed mode of self-identification is that it is based on the assumption that Indonesia is something fixed. In this essentialist perspective, Indonesia is perceived as an entity that has been around for the longest possible period of time and thus earns the point of stability. This is precisely what the regimes of Indonesian postcolonial state had been trying to do. They want their subjects

and others to believe them when they said that Indonesia is somehow a continuation of a certain glorious past under Majapahit Kingdom. Majapahit itself is a Hindu-Buddhist state that controlled the trade in Indonesian archipelago from the thirteenth to the fifteenth century. During its golden age, Majapahit's territorial influence included all Java, Bali, Sumatra, Kalimantan, Malay Peninsula, and some parts of Indochina. Majapahit was doomed as a result of the civil war and the spread of Islam. About the haunting influence of Majapahit on today's Indonesia, historian M.C. Ricklefs writes: "The memory of Majapahit's greatness has lived on in Indonesia, and it is sometimes seen as establishing a precedent for the present political boundaries of the Republic" (2001: 21-22).

Of course, the assumption that Indonesia is always there and stable is not true at all and misleading. Indonesia must, first of all, be understood as a modern invention. To do so what we need to do is simply taking a look at a very simple proof. The name "Indonesia" was not introduced by anyone from Majapahit era. It is not mentioned in *Negarakertagama*, a text widely believed to be the chronicle written during the heyday of that Hindu-Buddhist kingdom. The name "Indonesia" also cannot be found in any historical record from the period after Majapahit when kingdoms, one after the other, controlled the archipelago. In fact, it was a German ethnologist, Adolf Bastian, instead of a native educated or an Indonesian nationalist, who invented and introduced the name "Indonesia." Adolf Bastian in 1884 published his five-volumes book on the archipelago entitled *Indonesian oder die Inseln des Malaiischen Archipels* (Indonesia or the Islands of Malay Archipelago). However, even after the name was being introduced, it had not had

any political sense at all. It was invented to refer to a geographical designation (Subanar, 2000: 107-8).

As we will see, the first three decades of the twentieth century witnessed both new territorial definition of Indonesia and huge social and political transformation in regard to the birth of the national consciousness among its colonized subjects. During the period, the relation between that colony and its European motherland was entering a new phase where the first was now becoming more under direct rule of the later in its true political sense. The simple exploitative and monopolistic economic relations that had been the currency during the VOC era (1602-1799) were abandoned. VOC, standing for Vereenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie (United East Indies Company), was the chartered trade company that was given legitimacy by the Dutch crown to administer and monopolize its trade in its colony in today Indonesia. The end of the VOC era was signified by the more systematic militaristic expansions that were carried out to conquer independent regions and bring them into the possession of the King or Queen of the Netherlands (Ricklefs, 2001). One direct result of these enterprises is the production of the current map of geographical and political Indonesia. This further shows how the idea of Indonesia is not something very ancient. We can even say that Indonesia, as a political entity, is a modern invention resulted from actions taken by the colonizer.

In this chapter, I will explore the background and contexts for my discussion of the main character of Pramoedya Ananta Toer's the *Buru Quartet*, i.e. Minke, whom I will see, with the perspective I borrow from Lacan, as the metonymy of Indonesian nationalism.

The first part will be the historical background. Here, I will discuss the events that provide significant contribution to our understanding of Minke. This part will show the modern evolution of Indonesian nationalism. Minke is the character whose story is loosely based on historical Tirta Adhi Suryo (1880-1918). Tirta Adhi Suryo himself, widely renowned by his initial "TAS," was considered as the pioneer of Indonesian journalism. This is why, I will argue, that the character of Minke would be best understood by putting him in the historical context that surrounds his "patron." In other words, Minke's greatest aspiration of a just society where there is no exploitation of people over people, which would then constitute one of the most important aspects of his Indonesian dreams, owes to his historical situation as an educated native. An educated native was a peculiar state not common during Minke's era, making him a good example of hybridity where East and West meet and negotiate.

After putting Minke's story in its relevant historical context, the second part of my discussion on the backgrounds will be theoretical. As already implied, I will employ Lacanian perspective, and therefore this second part will focus on this French thinker's conception of the feeling of loss. Why the feeling of loss? I am aware that Lacan's contribution to the world of literary criticism can be very wide and deep, but I think his conception of the feeling of loss is particularly helpful in explaining of Minke's character development. In Lacanian sense, the term "the feeling of loss" refers to the situation when someone in the end realizes that what he/she used to perceive as the complete union with the mother in the Imaginary Order could not be sustained anymore as he or she gains

his/her sense of selfhood in the mirror stage of his/her development and is, consequently, able to articulate that traumatic experience of separation in a language. A good understanding of this feeling and the subsequent efforts to recuperate what was lost lends, I would argue, important insights into our explanation of Minke's experience of losses of his perceived union with his Javanese "traditional mother" and his dream of and total trust in his European "modern mother." The story does not end here since Minke's character development is also signified by his efforts to create or forge his own identity. And it is here in the later efforts of creating, forging, and inventing a new space of identity and not in the first ones when the feeling of loss prompts acts of recuperation where I will see the story of Minke as a metonymy to Indonesian *bildungsroman*. We must admit, therefore, that however important Lacanian conception of the feeling of loss it is not satisfyingly able to explain Minke's desire for a new society, which I will call "Indonesia." Minke's desire of Indonesia is a break from that cycle of simple recuperation of what was lost. Instead of dreaming of a reunion with his "mothers," he envisions a totally new society where everyone "becomes a free human being" (Toer, 1990a: 128).

In the last part of this chapter, I will briefly bring forward the synopsis of the Buru Quartet and introduce its list of characters. This part, in my opinion, is of necessity so that we—the writer and the readers—will be more or less stay on the same page in terms of the text that I am going to explore in this thesis. The relationships between those characters are actually more complex and interdependent than it seems or I am able to summarize here. And, each character has his/her own story that can lead into another great analysis. But for

practical reason of this thesis, I will put Minke in the central position and the other characters as supporting my analysis of that central character.

Historical Background: Putting Minke in Perspective

Pramoedya Ananta Toer (1925-2006) was more than a master of narrative. What he wrote during his lifetime, both fiction and non-fiction, are more than just a product of his creative imagination. Many, if not most, of his works talk about the history of modern Indonesia. And, he made a serious research for his writings. Pramoedya works are generally categorized as “socialist realism.” This is due to their primary concern on popular struggles. For Pramoedya, a literary work must talk about and for the people (Harjana and Junus, 1981: x). I think this is why today his works become one of the most important cornerstones in Indonesian literary history, which heavily influence other Indonesian writers as well as inspire many young Indonesians. Pramoedya’s works also have significant contribution to the understanding of Indonesian nationalism and beyond. It is almost not possible to have a good understanding about this nation and its society without reading and understanding Pramoedya’s works.

Pramoedya’s narratives, especially if we have access to read them in their original language, bahasa Indonesia or simply Indonesian, are also very rich from aesthetical point of view. But Indonesian, the lingua franca of people in Indonesia and the nation’s national language today, is not Pramoedya mother tongue. Pramoedya’s mother tongue is Javanese.

In Pramoedya's writings, Indonesian shows its dynamic, and sometimes its gibberish, nature. James T. Siegel (1997) is one among a few scholars who has particular interest in exploring this problem of Indonesian in Pramoedya's works. But most of the time, it is the content of Pramoedya's stories that fascinates, inspires, and challenges critics and scholars like Pheng Cheah (2003), Tony Day and Keith Foulcher (2002), and Peter Hitchcock (2010).¹ This thesis, too, deals more with the content of Pramoedya's the Buru Quartet. And because of the lack of better choices, it will use the English translation of Pramoedya's opus by Max Lane, which was firstly published in 1990 by Penguin Books.

Despite his deep interest in universal humanism as clearly can be inferred from two titles of his Buru Quartet *This Earth of Mankind* and *Child of All Nations*—implying Pramoedya's belief in universal humanistic ideals—that does not necessarily mean that Pramoedya hates nationalism and/or his homeland, Indonesia: “I have always been proud to be an Indonesian and a citizen of Indonesia and have carried myself with the awareness that I, too, contributed to the making of this nation” (Toer, 1999:36). He sees that Indonesia has a great potential to be a great nation, if not in reality then at least in its ideals. But, Pramoedya's love toward his country is not a blind love either. His being a

¹ Hypothetically, this is due to the fact that Indonesian as a language is still in the peripheral position of the global language's politics. Although spoken by more or less 230 million people across Indonesian territory, it is barely spoken by any other communities outside Indonesia. And moreover, Indonesian, the language developed from Malay—a vernacular spoken by minority people traditionally lived in the east coast of Sumatra, west coast of Borneo, and today Singapore and Malay Peninsula—is a still growing and developing language. It is a language in the making, which borrows a lot from other more stable languages. And as Keith Foulcher suggested, Malay is “the language of challenge” (1981: 9).

patriotic neither made him unable to see that there was something going wrong in the subsequent course of the nation, a betrayal toward the ideals of Indonesia by the postcolonial state, nor simply ignored the mistakes. He wanted to contribute something toward the making of Indonesia in its rightful path. Pramoedya wrote the *Buru Quartet* during his twelve-years exile in Buru Island in eastern part of Indonesia. Suharto's New Order regime accused Pramoedya as a sympathizer of PKI (Indonesian Communist Party), which was untrue at all. About this fact, Pramoedya in his memoir of his exilic years wrote: "I have never been a party man, never an organizational sort of person ... Even if the PKI wanted me to join, I wouldn't have. I won't be anyone's gofer" (Toer, 1999: xvi). Even though only from a distance, he intended that those works can be another contribution of his to "help correct the accepted colonial version of history of the rise of Indonesian nationalism" (Toer, 1999: 314). Pramoedya's love for (the ideals of) his nation and his honest criticism to the postcolonial regimes that he saw betraying those ideals had earned him several years in prisons during the Dutch, Sukarno, and Suharto's eras. Pramoedya was imprisoned from 1947 to 1949 by the Dutch because of his choice to support to the struggle of the young Indonesian Republic. Sukarno also put him in the jail for his criticism against that first President of Indonesia whom Pramoedya saw as acting like an old feudalistic Javanese king. And, we do not need to mention again how Suharto exiled him to the arid island of Buru for more than twelve years from 1967 to 1979 (<http://www.notablebiographies.com/supp/Supplement-Sp-Z/Toer-Pramoedya-Ananta.html>).

As a socialist realist, Pramoedya believes that a writer should not develop an escapist attitude toward the problems and affairs of the world and its people. A writer should write literature that deals with the struggle of the people. Literature thus shall take side to those of working class. “My words, my writing, my actions—they have never been for myself alone, either directly or indirectly. There is no such thing as an artist who creates art only for himself. That is masturbation. There’s a social aspect to it, and the greater development of the social aspect, the better it is” (Toer, 1999: 335). On the other hand, a man of letters like himself is not a historian. A writer cannot and shall not, like a historian, pretend that he or she is able to systematically produce an accurate historical account. A writer is also not an activist/politician either, whose primary concern is pragmatic or practical things and power-oriented. A writer like Pramoedya occupies another realm and has different social function. As a writer, what he should aim to do is not to expose the materiality of history or phenomenon as it is but to produce a reflection upon it—open and explore the spirit of the history for his/her reader. About this, Pramoedya writes: “And so there come to be a new reality, a literary reality, a downstream reality, whose origin was an upstream reality, that is, a historical reality. A literary reality (that) contains within it a reorientation and evaluation of civilization and culture, which is precisely not contained in the historical reality” (Toer, 1996: 4).

Following that suggestion of that notion, if we want to understand the literary reality or the downstream reality in the *Buru Quartet*, it is a necessary thing to explore and understand the historical reality or the upstream reality from where it springs off. A good

understanding of the opus' social and historical context is, therefore, very important.

That is why we should discuss—however briefly—the history of Indonesia that spans from the late nineteenth century to the first half of the twentieth century, which becomes the setting of time of the Buru Quartet.

To better understand the situation of that period, a little further flashback to the time of VOC, United East Indies Company, I think will be helpful. The bankruptcy of VOC in 1799 (Taylor, 2003: 209) had forced the Dutch crown to take over the affairs of its East Indies colony. Once a powerful and monopolistic trading company, VOC went bankrupt because of its internal corruption, mismanagement, and incapability of its staffs. In addition to those factors, according to historian M.C. Ricklefs, the bankruptcy of VOC was also prompted by other, external factors, i.e. the situation in Europe that was, during the later years of VOC, torn apart by Napoleonic wars, making the cost of maintaining faraway colonies like Indonesia far more expensive (Ricklefs, 2001:144). The transfer of power from VOC to the Dutch government can also be viewed as the transfer of the colony's people and resources to the crown. The Dutch crown then created its representation in Batavia, now Jakarta. A Governor General, directly appointed by the King or the Queen of the Netherlands, led this office of colonial representation. Under the Governor General, despite the long wars that torn Europe apart and put the mother country in a very difficult position among the giant powers of Europe (France and England), the expansionist policy of the colonial government in Indonesia did not stop. More and more once to be independent regions were taken over and integrated into the Dutch East Indies

colonial map. Historian Adrian Vickers in his *A History of Modern Indonesia* writes:

“By 1909 the Dutch had established an integrated territory. Many areas of the Indies were placed initially under military rule, which often amounted to establishing what one contemporary critic called dictatorships” (2005: 14).

These efforts of subjugation were almost always greeted with resistance from the local people and their leaders. The Javanese people, for instance, although they did not have a strong political and military structure following the division of their once a powerful traditional state into two weak sultanates in 1755, still showed some resistance against the Dutch. The Java War that was waged between 1825 and 1830 and led by Prince Diponegoro showed that common Javanese, as well as their princes and religious leaders, “hated the foreigners who travelled through their landscape and controlled their lives” (Taylor, 2003: 236). When the Javanese war ended, it left huge damage to both sides. Some reports say that from the colonial government side, 8,000 European and 7,000 Indonesian paid soldiers died and as many as 200,000 Javanese lost their lives, reducing the population of Java by half (Ricklefs, 2001: 153).

In West Sumatra, a religious movement took place at the turn of the nineteenth century following the suit of Wahhabi movement in Mecca.² Their leaders were popularly

² Wahhabism is an Islamic movement in Saudi Arabia in the 18th century. Founded by Abdul Al-Wahhab, it advocates the purging Islam of what is considered to be impurities and innovations. This movement has developed considerable influence in the Muslim world. The coming of Wahhabism in West Sumatra was through three hajjis who came home in 1803 from Mecca. They saw the impurities of Islam as practiced by the people around them. Wahhabism in West Sumatra, which took form

known as *padris*. This movement wanted to purify the Islam that was practiced with laxity by most of the Moslem community in that region. In the spirit aspect, *padris*' movement is probably comparable to that of Puritans who came to the New World in the sixteenth century. In their puritanical endeavors, the *padris* found a great resistance from the more secular community who adhered their *adat* (customary laws) over Moslem laws. The Dutch saw opportunity to take advantage of this enmity. They then involved themselves in the conflict by taking sides with the *adat* group. A war broke out soon after. This war happened from 1821 to 1838 (Ricklefs, 2001:183), with the *adat* group backed by the Dutch military force, as we might guess, emerged as the winner.

The militaristic expansion and, along with it, the process of geographical integration of the Dutch East Indies that took place in the whole nineteenth and early twentieth century happened elsewhere in Indonesia, too (Taylor, 2003: 209). It seems that no local kingdoms or leaders were able to contain that determined colonial progress. Traditional ways of fighting of the locals could not save themselves from European's muskets and bombs. So, one region followed by the others fell. Aceh in the northern tip of Sumatra was completely taken over in 1903 after a long and bloody war that lasted for thirty years (Vickers, 2005: 11). Bali and the islands around it were defeated later in the early twentieth century. Moluccas and most of Sulawesi, meanwhile, were already taken during the VOC era. If not with militaristic force, or as a complement to it, the expansion

in the Padri movement, opposed gambling, cock-fighting, matrimonial laws, the use of opium, tobacco, betel nut, and strong drink. But, different from their originator, Wahhabism in Indonesia did not oppose reverence for Islamic saints and the practice of visiting holy shrines (Ricklefs, 2001: 182-3).

and integration process made use another way: through Christian missionaries. This was what happened in Papua, several regions in North Sumatra, north Sulawesi, Moluccas, and western Kalimantan.

In the novel *Max Havelaar* (1860)—a work about the exploitation of Indonesian by the Dutch colonizer that became an inspiration for Pramoedya—its author, Multatuli (literally “I have suffered a lot”), writes how around the time when the novel was written, Indonesian regions could broadly be divided into two distinctive areas as regards the relationship of the mother country to the population. One was under the direct rule of the Netherlands’ crown, which included the whole of Java. The other was the most area outside Java Island where the local princes or kings had recognized the Netherlands as *suzerain*, but the daily administration was still under their full control (Multatuli, 1987: 66). This description could not be maintained anymore to accurately portray the situation of the second decade of the twentieth century, when almost all the regions that makes up Indonesia today had been united in one single political unit or entity named the Dutch East Indies, later to be Indonesia.

The Dutch East Indies government’s expansionist policy aiming to integrate Indonesia both geographically and politically proved to be very costly. Just as an illustration, the Aceh War alone had drained the government by as much as *f*400 million (which equals to around US\$10 billion today). The huge expenditure of those wars of conquest, combined with the already terrible economic and social situations in the mother country as a result of the lengthy Napoleonic Wars, have prompted the colonial

government to find ways to get “easy” money, not only to pay the soldiers but also to repay the Netherlands’ mounting debt. In order to get that “easy” money, in 1829 Johannes van den Bosch (1780-1844) proposed the initiation of *cultuurstelsel* (cultivation system). This policy decreed that each Indonesian family spared some percentage of their lands (around 20 in the beginning and then up to 33 percents in the later period) to cultivate and produce export crops, such as coffee, sugar, and indigo. Those who owned no plots of land were required to dedicate some days, or weeks, in a year in some government works, without receiving any payment or compensation. In theory, this policy seemed to be fair enough, especially since the government promised that it would make sure so that there would be no overdraft in the portion of land or time that its colonial subjects allocated. In practice, however, there was no real law enforcement. The carrying out of that original proposal was largely left to the interpretation of the local authorities, both Europeans and natives. It was not uncommon that they took more from the people than they should have (Ricklefs, 2001: 156-7). It is this horrendous picture of the cultivation system and its dire consequences on the lives of Indonesians that were portrayed very vividly in narratives like *Max Havelaar*.

From the perspective of the colonizer’s, however inhuman the practice of the cultivation system was, it was very profitable. Already in 1831, the colonial government was able to settle all the debts incurred by the VOC. From that year to 1877, the Dutch home treasury received revenue of f832 million. The percentage of revenue increased from time to time in comparison with the Dutch’s total revenue: 19 percent before 1850 to 32

percent in 1851-1860, to 34 percent in 1861-1866. These revenues kept the domestic economy afloat. They were able to pay off their debts, lower the taxes, build infrastructures, etc. In addition, Amsterdam became the world center of trade of sugar and coffee (Ricklefs, 2001: 159-60).

After several decades of practice, the cultivation system was later evaluated as narratives like *Max Havelaar* and some others brought to the wider audience at home the sad story of the exploitation of the people in the colony by the colonial government. This evaluation toward the cultivation system could not be separated from the political situation in the Netherlands. The last quarter of the nineteenth century the Netherlands witnessed the emergence of the Radicals. The members of this group were more liberal-minded. They started to win chairs in the parliament. In 1899, one of the Radicals' prominent figures, Th. van Deventer, wrote and published an article in the Dutch journal *de Gids* entitled "Een eereschuld" (A Debt of Honor). Th. van Deventer himself was a politician and lawyer who had spent 1880-1897 in Indonesia. The article van Deventer wrote has been viewed by some historians as marking the birth of the Ethical policy, which was formally launched by Queen Wilhelmina two years later in 1901 (Ricklefs, 2001: 193-4). The proponents of the Ethical policy, known as "Ethici" (Taylor, 2003: 283), believed that the Netherlands and its people owed a lot to the Indonesians who had been extracted their natural resources and manpower to produce export crops that earned money for them. The "Ethici" further suggested that there were three areas through which the Dutch government could start

paying their debt to the people of Indonesia. Those three areas were education, irrigation, and emigration.

It just comes naturally that the Ethical policy, as any other colonial policy, must be viewed with suspicion. Although its name and “history” might suggest something almost positive and benevolent, the Ethical policy was actually rooted in two seemingly paradoxical principles, i.e. humanitarian concern and economic advantage (Ricklefs, 2001: 193). The question is: How can these two “opposite things” be reconciled in one policy? One critical way to view the Ethical policy is seeing the advancement in the three areas of the colonial life mentioned above (education, irrigation, and emigration) was basically made with the colonizer’s interests in the minds of the policy makers. What were then the interests of the policy makers who formulized the Ethical policy? To answer this question, we can look at what really happened during to the colonial life during the era of the Ethical policy. What happened in the Ethical policy era was basically the introduction of capitalism in the Dutch East Indies. The Dutch colonial government opened the colony’s door widely for private investors—mainly but not limited from Europe, because there were also investors coming in from America and other places in the world—to come and exploit its natural resources and labors. The improvement in the area of irrigation, for example, was made to attract agricultural investors to come to Indonesia and grow the plants they thought would be profitable in European and world markets. It is one heritage of this policy, in my opinion, that we still have today in Indonesia several agricultural clusters such as tea in Puncak, West Java; tobacco in Deli, North Sumatra; and rubber in South

Sumatra and Lampung. The systematic and sometimes also forceful movement of people out of the overcrowded Java Island to outer islands, particularly Sumatra and Kalimantan—called emigration, or transmigration as appropriated by Suharto’s New Order—was also done to bring more labors to the European-owned plantations in those new places.

In the area of education, the unspoken but determined goal of the Ethical policy is to create a class of native people who were grateful and cooperative toward their European masters. With the provision of education to only a handful of chosen youths (mostly based on the social or material position of their fathers), the Dutch East Indies administration hoped that they could create a small, privileged local elite group or a local middle class that was properly western educated. As such, “they [the educated natives] could take over much of the work of Dutch civil servants, ... thus cutting administrative expenses, restricting Islamic ‘fanaticism,’ and ultimately creating an inspiring example for lower levels of Indonesian society” (Ricklefs, 2001: 199). Seen from the colonizer’s perspective, there were at least two reasons why colonial education was provided to just a very small percentage of native youths. One was to justify their endeavor of colonialism. This approach This implies how the Dutch colonizers must feel scrupulous about what they had done so far in the colony, but at the same time it enabled the Dutch colonizers to defend the atrocities undertaken during the era of colonial rule. They must realized that in reality what they did was simply extracting the richness of both natural and human resources of the colony and enriching themselves from those exploitations over others. And this reality

was completely different from what they preached to their children and neighbors back in Europe. In short, the reality was very different from the ideals. Educating few natives, they must have thought, could help them feeling a little bit better about themselves, especially when they needed to boast to the rest of the world that their presence in the colony did help the colonized people to be “civilized” members of the modern society. Kartini, an emancipated woman from this era and an Indonesian national heroine today, is a great example of how the Ethici took pride in their efforts of educating the natives. Kartini learned Dutch, studied some simple Western ideas, two things which in turn enabled her to express her thoughts in the Dutch written form. Her correspondence with several prominent Dutch figures in her era made up a book, *Letters of a Javanese Princess* (first published in 1912 in Dutch). This compilation was widely cited as the hard proof that the Ethici proudly presented to anyone doubting the benefit of colonialism for the colonized. The other reason of the provision of education for a small number of Indonesians, as mentioned earlier, was to provide the colonial government with “nuts, screws, and bolts” for their machine of colonialism (Toer, 1990a: 17).

Now, how successful was the improvement in education from the perspective of the colonized? If we talk from the quantitative point of view, we may say that the provision of education for the colonized did not reach most of them. But that could be expected anyway. In 1905, or four years after the official implementation of the Ethical policy, only 36 Indonesians entered HBS (Hoogere Burgerschool, Higher middle-class school). Despite lingering doubt on statistics from that time period, the 1930 census shows that adult

literacy in Indonesia was only 7.4 percent. Their Dutch literacy was even lower, i.e. 0.32 percent (Ricklefs, 2001: 201). And talking from a more qualitative point of view, as can be read from the conclusion historian M.C. Ricklefs made about the colonial education provided during the Ethical policy era: “Education produced neither a grateful and cooperative new elite nor a buoyant new spirit among the masses; ... Education produced some able and loyal officials, but it also produced a tiny dissatisfied elite who led the anticolonial movements” (2001: 203). Benedict Anderson made a very interesting observation about the role of education and the first generation of educated natives in promoting colonial nationalism:

“In the colonies ... youth meant, above all, the *first* generation ... to have acquired a European education, marking them off linguistically and culturally from their parents’ generation, as well as from the vast bulk of their colonized agemates. ... By ‘Youth’ we mean ‘Schooled Youth,’ at least at the start. This in turn reminds us again of the unique role played by colonial school-systems in promoting colonial nationalisms” (1991: 119).

It is in this historical context that our main character of the Buru Quartet, Minke, narrates his story. He lives in the defining moments of the turn of the nineteenth to twentieth century. He is a member of an elite group of the then Indonesian society that has a privileged access to European education. As a son of a “bupati” (literally, regent), he is expected to become one himself when he finishes his study. As a child of the Ethical policy, many put their hope on his shoulders, expecting that he would be an “intermediary” between the European master and the Indonesian masses. But something (or some things)

significant leads him to a very different direction. His dream is a break from the others’.

His dream is an Indonesian humanistic society, inspired by the spirit of the French Revolution he was thought at school, where everyone “becomes a free human being, not given orders, not giving orders” (Toer, 1990a: 128). It is this democratic society that he also proudly talks about to his mother and that he thinks should be the basic for the society he wants to create.

Theoretical Perspective: Explaining Minke Using Lacan

As a philosopher and thinker, Jacques Lacan’s thoughts (1901-1981) are not easy to understand. Lois Tyson in her book *Critical Theory Today* admits this fact: “Lacan’s work is rather abstract, often ambiguous, and almost always difficult to understand. In fact, he [Lacan] claimed that writing about the unconscious should be ambiguous and difficult to understand because the unconscious is itself ambiguous ... and is difficult to understand” (2006: 26). But, since what we want to discuss in this thesis is basically the unconscious, inner development of Minke, and how this development can be seen the metonymy for Indonesian nationalism’s *bildungsroman*, Lacan’s works, particularly the one related to that topic, I believe, will lend a great help. And although Lacan was primarily a psychoanalyst and psychiatrist, his works undeniably have profound impacts on literary studies and criticisms and beyond.

I do not pretend that I will employ Lacan's rich and complex thoughts in their depth and entirety in this thesis. I will instead use only his perspective that I think will be helpful to understand Minke's character development in particular and Indonesian national consciousness in general. And that perspective is Lacan's conception of the feeling of loss or lack. In Minke's character development, he experiences two significant feelings of loss: one is the loss of the perceived perfect union with his traditional identity which happens when his mother banishes him from Javanese culture and calls him a "brown Dutchman" and the other is the loss of his perceived perfect (dream of) unity with Western or European modernity.

This thesis is built around the hypothesis that the *Buru Quartet* is the *bildungsroman* of Minke and that the story of Minke is, or can be seen as, the metonymy of Indonesian history. *Bildungsroman* itself, as a literary term, can generally be defined as a work that narrates how the main character matures and develops from a simple young man or woman to a more complicated and informed adult through his or her education, both formally, or in an educational institution, and informally, or through his or her contact and interaction with events and other characters (Cuddon, 1999: 81-82). The *Buru Quartet* is such a thing: it narrates the story of how Minke matures and develops. And it is in this discussion of Minke's character development that we can employ Lacanian conception of the feeling of loss.

At this point, let us start with a very brief discussion on Lacanian psychological development of an infant. At the beginning, according to Lacan, the infant experiences

“both itself and its environment as a random, fragmented, and formless mass” (Tyson, 2006:27). In this period, the infant cannot differentiate itself from its environment.

Everything is one and yet unidentifiable. Perhaps, this stage is what Slavoj Zizek refers as the “Real,” where the “grey and formless mist, ... the pulsing of the presymbolic substance in its abhorrent vitality” lies (1991: 14-15). Still according to Zizek, it is also something “outside” whose existence we can see from “inside,” but when we are finally tempted to go outside, it blurs away and what we get is only a chaotic existence we cannot really grasp. Staying in the “inside” is the only way of existence at this stage.

This presymbolic stage, so called due to the incapability of the infant to produce and/or understand symbols, ends when the infant, between age of six and eight months old, experiences what Lacan calls the *Mirror stage*. Here, as the result of seeing its own reflection on the “mirror,” either in its real or figurative sense, the infant develops a sense of itself as a whole rather than a formless and fragmented mass. But, the infant does not have words to express its feeling, since it is, too, still preverbal stage. This stage is also known as the *Imaginary Order*. Here, the child, through perception, feels that he or she is complete or full and that he or she is united with the mother. The mother is all that the child needs, as it holds true of the opposite. In Zizek’s discussion, this stage probably refers to the realm of “Reality,” with capital “R,” an ontological condition prior to the invention of language. The dominant feelings in this stage are the indescribable feelings of fullness, complete and ultimate union. But, of course, this union is only a perceived completeness instead of objective one.

The moment of language acquisition signifies a paramount change in the child's psychological development according to Lacan's theory. It becomes the initiation into the *Symbolic Order*, "for language is first and foremost a symbolic system of signification, that is a symbolic system of meaning-making" (Tyson, 2006: 28). As a result of this, the child begins to be able to articulate his/her selfhood. The child can now assert his identity as separated entity from others, also from the figure of the mother. But this process of the awakening of that self-hood consciousness also, at the same time, involves an experience of separation from others, and the biggest separation of which is the separation from the perceived intimate union with the mother. For Lacan, this separation constitutes the child's biggest experience of loss. And that experience will then haunt the child for the rest of his/her life. The child will consequently seek substitutes, big and small, to recuperate this greatest loss. Lacan calls these substitutes *objet petit a*. Each and every person has his/her own personal *objet petit a*, and each is intended to recuperate the loss felt inside. But as the language or, in Zizekian terms, the symbolic, that is acquired is never able to fully represent Reality, so is not *objet petit a* completely able to substitute what has lost.

The efforts of substituting what has lost are, therefore, past-oriented. What is desperately wanted to be recuperated lies in the past, or, to be more precise, in imagined or romanticized past. The harsh fact that we can never go back to the past prompts us to romanticize it. We start to dream and build our imagination of the glorious past. We put and understand our existence around our imagination of the past. The past of our imagination is where we want to be once again. The present and the future will feel like a

foreign land, an exile. The past of our imagination is, therefore, not the same with the past as a matter of fact. The loss of the romanticized past is like the loss of the home.

Indonesian nationalism, as already mentioned, tries to justify its existence by appropriating the glorious past of Majapahit Kingdom. Seen this way, Indonesian nationalism is to many scholars past-oriented. If we are to strictly and faithfully follow Lacan, we may come to such a conclusion. Pheng Cheah, for example, in his discussion on nationalism, mentions that nationalism is a threat to human life (2003:1) because of its fixed gaze on the frozen past. The failure of many postcolonial states in Africa, Asia, and South America to deliver their promises, as well as their tendency to fall into practicing the old colonialist modes of exploitation under new local regime—popularly known as neocolonialism—seems to affirm that what nationalism does is simply recuperating what has lost in and because of the colonial era.

The next question is how we can we see Minke's story or his character development, which is heavily signified, or probably tainted, by the experiences of loss and their subsequent efforts of recuperation in the *Buru Quartet*, as the metonymy of the history of Indonesian nationalism. What is metonymy? And how can Minke's character development be seen as a metonymy to Indonesian *bildungsroman*?

Metonymy is a literary term defined as the process of using an object associated with or part of another object as the stand-in for the whole object or vice versa (Cuddon, 1999: 510 and Baldick, 1990: 135). In literary study, metonymy typically takes form as

synecdoche, where we use the part of a thing to talk about or to get sense of the thing as a whole. Some examples of metonymy, or synecdoche, include the “Crown” for the monarchy, the “Bench” for the judiciary, and “Dante” for his works. In Lacanian perspective, metonymy is one of two processes in language where the unconscious, which once again is heavily characterized by the feeling of loss and desire to recuperate it, works. The other process is called metaphor. Metaphor is a process in language when one object is used as the stand-in for another, dissimilar object to which we want to nevertheless compare it (Tyson, 2006:29-30). One famous example of metaphor is “red rose” that is widely used in literature as the stand-in for a different thing, which is love.

In observing Minke and Indonesian nationalism, I see, as already suggested several times above, the metonymic relation between the two. In this sense, Minke’s story is a metonymy for Indonesian national awakening history. How can this be? First of all, both Minke and Indonesian nationalism share the characteristics of *bildungsroman*. They are organic entities, something in the making, something in progress, and characterized by the processes of “(personal) development and (educational) maturity” (Childs and Fowler, 2006: 18-19). But since Indonesian nationalism is an abstract idea impossible to be understood in an exhaustive way, discussion about Minke’s *bildungsroman*, which is more concrete and tangible, I argue, would be helpful in providing insights into our understanding of Indonesian nationalism. The fact that what we would get is simply an accumulation or sum of pieces of understanding or insight into the whole should not discourage or refrain us from our efforts to explain the story of Indonesian nationalism.

After all, in Lacanian parole, the Reality can never be explained thoroughly through the Symbolic. There will always be things escape, or unexplainable. If the Minke's story is seen as the language for Indonesian's story, we must be satisfied with a better understanding and not the best one.

Pramoedya himself seemed to endorse the possibility of using Minke's character development, or any literary characters in his novels for that matter, as the metonymy of Indonesian nationalism. In the introduction of his personal journals or memoir from the years in Buru exile under the title of *The Mute Soliloquy* (1999), Pramoedya wrote, "[A]n individual's personal and sensory perceptions [and stories] ... form one part of that person's nation's history and humankind in general." The similar tone can also be inferred from his essay "My Apologies, in the Name of Experience" (1996) which concludes that literary reality is sprung from, and therefore is not entirely separated from, the historical reality, that literary reality can shape our understanding of and influence our attitude toward the historical reality, and that at some points the truth of fiction is also the truth of history.

Both Minke and Indonesian nationalism, as suggested above, are organisms striving to maximize their capacity for life. Their struggles against the colonial (and neocolonial) states are life's struggle against all that negates and obstructs their dynamism and causes their negation (Cheah, 2003: 252). In short, Minke's character development can help us understanding the birth of Indonesian idea and dream.

Minke's Story: A Synopsis

As suggested by its popular epithet, the *Buru Quartet* was written during its author's exile in Buru Island. Buru is the third largest island of Indonesian's Moluccas province after Seram and Halmahera. In the late 1960s when Pramoedya was sent there by the militaristic regime under Suharto (1921-2008), it was "a virtually undeveloped island" (Toer, 1999: xx). Around 12,000 political prisoners of category 'B' were sent there, with Pramoedya among those of the first shipload. Until 1973, Pramoedya was severed from the world of literature. He was denied of any access to writing material and all letters that came to him from the outside world and vice versa were heavily censored. His daily routine includes physical works of opening paddy fields and building roads and bridges. Comparing his situation and the earlier Indonesian nationalists, he wrote: "Nationalists exiles sent by the Dutch Indies government to Digul, ... and other parts of the country in the 1930s were provided financial support. But here, in the middle of this fruitless savannah, we political prisoners were forced to survive by intuition" (Toer, 1999: 39).

In 1973, Pramoedya was allowed to write again and provided with paper and stationary needed, but that does not mean that he could write anything that he wanted. Even after his release from the exile in 1979, the regime still put him in a house of glass and all his writings were under heavy scrutiny, with many of them ended in the blacklists. The *Buru Quartet* was banned not very long after its first publication in Indonesia in 1980 because of a cliché: he was seen as subtly propagating Marxism, Leninism, and Communism through his works (Harjana and Unus, 1981: 23, 35). Pram was even

compared to Muso and D.N. Aidit, two Indonesian communist leaders. Not until the long-awaited end of Suharto regime in 1998 could Pramoedya be a “free” man again.

The Buru Quartet was translated into English by Max Lane, an Australian diplomat and scholar, and published in 1999 by Penguin publisher. This quartet has a paramount importance for everyone who wants to have a better understanding of Indonesian history in particular and the postcolonial situation in general. The Buru Quartet comprises of four books: *This Earth of Mankind*, *Child of All Nations*, *Footsteps*, and *House of Glass*.

The first three books tell from the first person point of view how Minke develops from a naïve young man who admires everything that comes through his European teachers to a mature man who is critical of colonial power as well as of the traditional Javanese values. The first book begins with a very interesting remark that shows how Minke is very proud to be a son of European enlightenment: “I was still very young, just the age of a corn plant, yet I had already experienced modern learning and science: They bestowed upon me a blessing whose beauty was beyond description” (Toer, 1990a: 16). But throughout the story, he experiences a great deal of things and learns from his interactions with other characters of the quartet that European was not as sincere as he might think regarding their civilization mission. The lost of his wife to European colonial law acts like a gong for his ever-increasing suspicion toward his European teachers, signifying the total break from his “cultural mother”: “Europe, you, my teacher, is this the manner of your deeds?” (Toer, 1990a: 358).

Minke's character development is heavily influenced by "teachers" that surround him. Magda Peters, his favorite teacher in HBS, is a member of the Radicals who teaches Minke to be critical to the European colonialism. Nyai Ontosoroh, Minke's mother-in-law, whose tragic experience being sold by her own father to a Dutch official has empowered her to learn the "master's ways" and use them to emancipate herself, is his source of inspiration and strength in his struggle against colonialism. Kammer and Jean Marais are two people who constantly challenge Minke to study his own people, listen their stories. It is also these two close friends of his that push Minke to take a path that nobody ever passes it before: writing and publishing a Malay (printed) newspaper. His association with Ter Haar, a radical journalist, also helps opening Minke's eyes to the capitalistic nature of the colonialism and how he should deal with it. Khouw Ah Soe, a young Chinese oversea activist, makes Minke understand that he should start organize Indonesian people if they ever want to free themselves from colonialism. His friendship with early Indonesian nationalists is also influential in shaping his conception about how Indonesian nationalism should be materialize.

The fourth and last book, *House of Glass*, is narrated from a totally different perspective, since Minke, as the voice of the emancipated native, is sent to exile by the colonial regime in the end of the third book. The task of narrating the story is put in the mouth of a high police official, Pangemanann, who masterminds the efforts of surveillance of all nationalistic movements within the Dutch East Indies colony. The story is thus now told from the regime's perspective. By far, this book is the most critical of the four toward

the colonial and neocolonial enterprises and not few who see it as a Pramoedya's indirect criticism toward Suharto's regime with all its silencing policy.

Chapter 2

Hybridity as An Exilic Experience

“Brown is impurity” (Richard Rodriguez)

I deliberately open this chapter with a short excerpt by Richard Rodriguez (born 1944), the Hispanic American writer. I do so because Rodriguez is a good example of a writer who personally experiences that his being brown is something problematic, an uneasy position. Being brown, according to Rodriguez, is problematic at least for two reasons. Firstly, it is like occupying the position in the middle between being white—the symbol of the power, wealth, and educated—and being black—the common representation of the powerless, poor, and uneducated. He does not feel that he can easily and freely float in-between of these two polar or binary identities. Rodriguez is neither White nor Black. His being brown, therefore, also refers to his ambiguous position between his Mexican or parental cultural heritage and what commonly viewed as the American way. Because of his participation in the US formal education in his hometown in California, Rodriguez has learned how to speak and communicate with others in English, the language his family don't speak to him at home, which is Spanish. From his childhood, Rodriguez must constantly shift between these two identities, these two places he could not easily

reconcile. He feels ambiguous about them and constantly asks himself about his own place amid these social and cultural constellations surrounding him (Rodriguez, 2002: xi).

To some extents, Minke of Pramoedya Ananta Toer's the Buru Quartet, as we will discuss in this chapter, also experiences such an ambiguous, in-between position as experienced by Rodriguez. We already knew that Minke comes from and is reared in a traditional Javanese family. In and by his family, Minke is of course introduced to Javanese culture and values. And then he is sent away from that family to a totally new cultural space: a Dutch school. In that colonial institution, Minke is taught to think differently and to speak differently, with different language. The discussion of this chapter will, therefore, rotate around how Minke deals with his ambiguous, in-between position. We will answer questions like: Can he reconcile the Javanese and the Dutch cultures and values, or at least easily "oscillate" in that exilic space? How does he see his being hybrid, of not totally West but not wholly East either? What happens with Minke's being Javanese and what happens with his desire to embrace modernity in its totality? This chapter will particularly focus on the melancholic side of hybrid identity as Minke's identity. In exploring and explaining this nature, I will use Edward Said's perspective on exile. I argue that the situation of being hybrid comparable to the situation in exile with an intense dream of coming "home." Of course, this dream of ever coming home is perfectly a dream without reality because what is home but the past of which we had departed and which we can only romantically imagined without ever being able to recuperate wholly. People who experience hybridity and who are in exile perceive their current situation as an

intermediary state between leaving home and coming back home (again). Being in exile and being hybrid refer to the similar kind of experience: living in a foreign land. Culturally speaking, both exile and hybrid people occupy a nervous space of identity. Furthermore, Said describes the exilic situation as a consequence of modernity, where the homeland of tradition has been left behind or abandoned while the new home is not yet achieved or any idea about arrival at the new home is always viewed with suspicion.

The Story of the Name “Minke”

To explain the downsides or the melancholic aspects of hybrid identity, exploring the name “Minke” can be a good start. The name “Minke” is, in my opinion, a too interesting case to be ignored in our discussion of hybridity. First of all, the choice of “Minke” as the main character of the *Buru Quartet* needs some intellectual visit. We may want to question as to why is it “Minke” and what does the peculiar name signify?

As the author, Pramoedya himself interestingly opens the *Buru Quartet* with a short self-introduction of Minke. He does it as if he wants to highlight the importance and the peculiarity of that name. To a certain degree, Pramoedya sounds like a detective-story writer to me: “People called me Minke. My own name ... for the time being I need not to tell it. Not because I’m crazy for mystery. I’ve thought about it quite a lot: I don’t yet really need to reveal who I am before the eyes of others.” (Toer, 1990a: 15). This introduction sounds very simple. However, at the same time, it also sounds mysterious.

And the mysterious thing, being wrapped in its simple and common disguise to “deceive” and surprise its audiences—this we can learn from any detective story and movie—usually contains some secret of high importance. In our case, the important information is hypothetically related to our main character and narrator.

To help illustrating my point, we might compare “Minke” with other famous work by Edgar Allan Poe (1809-1849) entitled “Purloined Letter” (1844).³ In the latter work, the letter in question—the mystery and the secret information it contains—is not, as we might expect, hidden under the table, in the crack of the wall, or inside of a shelf, or somewhere else people commonly deem safe and secret. It is simply, almost carelessly, put in the open space. The mystery is treated like a common, everyday thing: openly exposed.

The similar mode of “disguising” the mystery in the open can also be found in the story of the name “Minke.” That mystery seems to be said out loud so that casual readers might not even realize that there is something important put right under their noses. Careful readers, on the other hands, sense the strangeness and may question: Why does not Minke want to reveal his “real” name and/or identity then and there, if it exists at all? What is the meaning and significance of the name “Minke?” What happens then to his old, and supposedly “real,” name? What is actually happening here? The narrator’s reluctance to

³ The short story tells about the potentially scandalous letter purloined of a certain illustrious person by Minister D__. The police try to get back the letter by making a thorough and systematic investigation in the house of Minister D__, but could not find the letter. The narrator’s friend, Dupin, however is able to retrieve the letter because he applies a simple principle of following the mind of Minister D__: conceal something important in a self-evident way so that it misses every body else’s expectation.

disclose Minke's real identity in reality acts like an invitation to its readers to discover his underlying motive or possibly vulnerable situation.

The Javanese—the ethnic group where Minke comes from and grows up—are not in agreement with Shakespeare's famous saying: "What is in a name?" For a Javanese, one's name is an important part of his or her identity as a member of a particular social and cultural group (Toer, 1990a: 78). And with little effort, I can show that both semantically and phonetically the name "Minke" is not a Javanese name. Semantically, a "true" Javanese name is, as suggested, a name with meaning. It carries the hope or expectation of its bearer's parents or community for the person. The name "Sastrotomo," for example, is a Javanese name because it carries the meaning of "respected person ... who could read and write" (Toer, 1990a: 79). Phonetically, a Javanese male name usually ends in "o" voice, like my own name "Dono," suggesting that I am a Javanese, or "an" voice, like "Paiman." "Minke" is not a recognizable word in Javanese vocabulary. So, Minke who is a Javanese does not have a Javanese name (anymore).

On the other hands, "Minke" is not a Western, or a Dutch, name either. "Minke" is not one not because the name does not carry meaning or rhyme in a certain way, which is a common characteristic of most Western names. It is not a Western name because the bearer does not have, or lacks of, the family name. Minke lacks of a vital part of Western civilization. This lack is particularly exposed when Minke must introduce himself to Europeans or educated natives. Minke stammers and feels nervous because he cannot provide them with his surname. One example is when Minke makes his first visit to Nyai

Ontosoroh's—his future mother-in-law and most important mentor—house. Here, Minke introduces himself to the children of the family, Robert and Annelies Mellema. “[Robert] still held my hand, waiting for me to give my family name. He raised his eyebrows” (Toer, 1990a: 25). The lack of the family name makes Minke feel unconfident and insecure among them. This example shows that Minke is “not yet” a Western name. The name shows that the bearer has left his old, traditional realm of identity and not yet fully arrived at the desired, modern identity of Europe. “Minke” stuck in-between.

Added to our previous finding, we understand that the name “Minke” is neither a Javanese name nor a European. We may now question: so what is Minke and how does this new, strange kind of name come into being? The subsequent narration in *This Earth of Mankind* informs us that “Minke” is indeed an invented name, further confirming that the name is neither a Javanese nor a Western one.

“Minke” is originally a degrading appellation and an inflected form of the standard, stable language. The birth and occurrence of the name “Minke,” however, is a curious case since it is not invented, as we might expect of a degrading name like that, in the marketplace or in some other obscure places. The name “Minke” is in fact invented at school, in that highly honorable institution of colonial education, by an educated European. Mr. Rooseboom, our main character's E.L.S. (Middle school) teacher, yells out the name “Minke” to him in front of his classmates, originally to mean “monkey,” with “... eyes popped out frighteningly” (Toer, 1990a: 39). The nickname, from that day on, despite our main character's strong suspicion that it has a pejorative meaning—at least initially—and

that it “meant something unpleasant,” interestingly turns into his most important mode of self-identification.

“[E]veryone in the class called me Minke. ... My teachers followed suit. Then my friends from all the other classes. Also from outside school. ... My grandfather didn't know Dutch. He couldn't even read or write Latin. He only knew Javanese, written and spoken. His view was that Minke should be my permanent name: It was a sign of respect from a good and wise teacher. So my real name was almost lost.” (Toer, 1990a: 39-40)

The appropriation of the new, non-Javanese, non-Dutch name happens at the cost of the loss of Minke's real name. He no longer lives in his old identity, i.e. Javanese identity, and, at the same time, he is not accepted as a full-fledged member of the identity he wishes to join, i.e. European identity. Minke feels he does not belong to both. He lives in suspension. To go back to where we started of our discussion, Minke, I will therefore argue, actually does not only reluctant to reveal his real name but he cannot do it since he does not have one (anymore). It will not be an easy and sincere thing for him, for example, to simply state that his name is Tirto Adhi Surjo—the historical character that inspires Pram to create Minke—because he must have realized that he is no longer his old self.

The invention of the name “Minke” is just one example of hybridity in the early twentieth century colonial Indonesia as a result of the colonial education. Several European-style schools were open to natives like Minke. Native students, coming from various cultural backgrounds, were introduced to and then must deal with new culture, new knowledge, and new ideas. The hybridity the process of mixing two or more cultures

creates may, in Homi Bhabha's terms, carry the possibility of "revaluation of the assumption of the colonial identity" (1994: 112). But although hybridity, generally defined as the situation of mix of a bit of this and a bit of that, seems positive when being viewed this way, in reality this situation does entail a deep feeling of loss in the parts of the hybrid people. What is lost is, as is exemplified by the loss of Minke's real name, the perceived rootedness, or the sense of belonging to one pure and stable cultural space or identity. Hybridity is, therefore, heavily tainted by the "impurity." Or, to follow Richard Rodriguez's idea, it is neither black nor white in their strict sense; it is brown, a mix of them (Rodriguez, 2002). The name "Minke," as we have seen, is neither anchored in the presumably pure Javanese identity nor "real" Dutch or English. It is not-completely-East-not-wholly-West. It is a neurotic, insecure condition signified by the feeling of being exiled or banished or uprooted from both sides of cultural identities. This neurotic nature of being hybrid can also be inferred from Ian Chambers' definition, which suggests that the process of the creation of hybridity is always "open and incomplete, involving a continual fabulation, invention, and construction in which, finally, there is no fixed identity or final destination" (Cohen, 2008: 133).

To properly understand the complexity of Minke's hybridity, I believe an exploration on how and why Minke finally decides to leave his parents' cultural identity, the Javanese identity, is necessary. An exploration like that will give us information about what factors motivate him to leave his parents' house. Does he leave his traditional, parental house without any tinge of sadness? Is Minke ready with the consequences of

living uprooted from his own inherited identity? Does the hybrid identity he arrive at later the one he really look for? Or is it simply a compromise?

The Story of a Departure (without Arrival)

Minke, who comes from a Javanese aristocrat family, faces many new ideas and things when he enters a colonial school. In this Western-style educational institution, Minke is introduced to modern knowledge that significantly alters the course of his character development. As a result of his introduction to modernity, he becomes a different person from his old self and also from his fellow Javanese. About his experience at school, Minke writes: “This science and learning, which I had been taught at school and which I saw manifested in life all around me, meant that I was rather different from the general run of my countrymen” (Toer, 1990a: 16).

The question is, however, what is Javanese identity, or what is that which he refers as “the general run of my countrymen,” of which Minke departs. Answers to these questions are important because Javanese identity, I will argue, somehow significantly contributes to the creation of the hybrid Minke. How Minke perceives Javanese identity is also important to explain why he wants to leave it. As to with any other identity or cultural space, it is very tempting to assume that Javanese identity is A or B, or like this and that, or not this and not that. We tend to want to get an easy answer and that becomes one of the reasons we make generalization. But as we agree that identity is dynamic, we should see

Javanese identity likewise. The Javanese cultural space is, in other words, not as static an identity as some might suspect. The Javanese identity is a set of general codes of Javanese people, which is extracted from a long and common social, historical, economic, political experience that, in the meantime, is still going on and may have no real end result. At the same time, the process of essentialization, or calcification, in Javanese identity is also its unavoidable characteristic due to necessity (Brazier and Mannur, 2003: 233). When talking about Javanese identity, one will inevitably recall some of that identity's general features, characteristics, and "nature," which separate it from other solid and stable modes of identification.⁴

It is because of this latter process that if we compare Javanese identity to Minke's (new) hybrid identity, we will find out that the first is relatively more solid, safer, and "predictable." And it is only logical, while assuming that human beings tend to search for stability, to expect that Minke, like most people, feels nervous upon deciding to depart from such a stable identity to embrace another identity that is new. This is more so especially because the daunting possibility of never arriving at another point of stability

⁴ Stuart Hall might lend us his useful insight to understand these two seemingly paradoxical processes of a cultural identity formation. Minke's Javanese identity—or any other identity for that matter—can be understood as something that is framed by two axes or vectors. Both are simultaneously operative. The first is the vector of similarity and continuity, while the other is the vector of difference and rupture. The first one gives some grounding in, or some continuity with, the past. Meanwhile, the second reminds us that what we share is precisely the experience of a profound discontinuity. (Brazier and Mannur, 2003: 233-37). The Javanese identity, therefore, is both static and dynamic. It is both ever changing and desiring for stability.

that signifies the new identity. Thus if Minke finally makes his mind to let go off his Javanese identity, he must have a good reason to do so. When leaving his parents' home, what Minke abandons is the privileged status as a member of aristocracy in the colonial Indonesia. As someone with "the blood of the king of Java running in him" (Toer, 1990a: 120), he is a member of the local elite class. As such, he will be well respected and all his needs and interests will be catered. "Everyone bowed in respect. Perhaps among them there were some already sizing me for their son-in-law or brother-in-law" (Toer, 1990a: 137). But for Minke, that is not the world that he really wants. He makes a conscious choice and claims, "The world of priyayi, Javanese aristocrats ... was not my world. ... My world was not rank and position, wages and embezzlement. My world was this earth of mankind and its problems" (Toer, 1990a: 125). Up to this point, we may wonder: what's wrong with Javanese identity, or is Minke getting crazy?

From the narration of the *Buru Quartet*, we find out that aspects of the Javanese culture that Minke really despises as a result of his introduction to and immersion into modern knowledge are its feudalistic and patriarchal characteristics. The *Quartet* is full with textual evidences that suggest how Minke now critically sees his inherited culture. His deep admiration to universal humanistic and egalitarian ideals of the great French Revolution makes him feel uneasy with humiliating practices of a man upon others he finds particularly strong in the Javanese culture. For instance, when he is "kidnapped" one early morning from Nyai Ontosoroh's house and escorted and summoned to his father's house in the dawn of his inauguration as a *Bupati* (literally, Regent) of B__, Minke

expresses his great uneasiness: “What’s the point in studying European science and learning, mixing with Europeans, if in the end one has to cringe anyway, slide along like a snail, and worship some little king who is probably illiterate to boot” (Toer, 1990a: 121).

And since this practice has been there for several generations among Javanese people,

Minke further blames his ancestors:

“Truly, my friends would ridicule me if they could see this play, where a human being, who normally walks on his two whole legs, on his own feet, now has to walk with only half his legs, aided by his two hands. *Ya Allah!* You, my ancestors, you: What is the reason you created customs that would so humiliate your own descendants? You never once gave it any thought, you my ancestors who indulged in these excesses! Your descendants could have been honored without such humiliation! How could you bring yourself to leave such customs as a legacy?” (Toer, 1990a: 121-2).

To give a better understanding of those Javanese culture and identity which Minke views with critical eyes, I think the narration that we can find in the fourth book of the Quartet, *House of Glass*, can shed light.⁵ Minke of the Buru Quartet lives in the turn of the nineteenth century to the twentieth century. Historically, Minke’s era was more than two and half centuries after the two failed attempts by the Javanese to expel the VOC (Dutch East Indies Company) from Jakarta in 1628 and 1630 and around seven decades after the Javanese War led by Diponegoro in 1825 to 1830 ended with the leader’s exile (Ricklefs, 2001: 39, 59, 151). As a direct result of those failures, the morale of the Javanese people

⁵ The fourth book of the Buru Quartet is, in my opinion, more “technical” than the other three because it deals with several issues in a more expository way. The narrative is told from the point of view of Pangemanann, the chief police of the Dutch East Indies. In this book, Minke, although still becomes the center of the hub of the story, has been pushed out into an exile.

was at its lowest. As a community, they lost their self-esteem and self-confidence. They subsumed themselves under the complete rule of the Dutch colonial government. Two Javanese kingdoms in the central Java, Yogyakarta and Surakarta, were powerless both politically and economically. But, the problem with the Javanese people and their culture is deeper and more profound than it superficially looks, as Meneer L___, the colonial archivist, says to Pangemanann, the narrator of the fourth book of the *Buru Quartet*:

“When you start with the wrong philosophy, ... all that is left is to defend yourself. The Javanese have never gone on the offensive against the white. All they have been able to do is put up a defense, to hold the fort. But they were always defeated, because they held to a defeated philosophy. ... All that is left is that accommodating, compromising character. They can’t even put up any kind of self-defense anymore. ... It is very sad, but they themselves don’t even understand their own situation. They can only do that by comparing themselves with other peoples. Their writings over the last hundred years are the writings of a defeated people who do not want to escape from their defeat. There is no one who will suggest that they learn from Europe, or they even pretend that they do not know that Europe has them in its grip” (Toer, 1990d: 80).

Minke does not feel proud to be member of a defeated society like the Javanese. The Javanese community at Minke’s time was lagged behind in terms technological advancement and philosophical complexity compared to European whose achievements he learns at school and looks upon with great awe. No wonder that with all those negativities of the Javanese culture, Minke seems more than ready to give up his membership in the Javanese community: “What’s the use of being Javanese only to have one’s rights violated? ... I’m quite able even to leave behind this whole family” (Toer, 1990a: 128-9). Minke hates his Javanese identity both because of the inferior position of the Javanese

relatively to the Dutch and the authoritarian and paternalistic features of the culture as embodied by his father and brother. To Minke, his father and brother who are rank-oriented and petty minded are the representation of the Javanese value he detests; it is a mentality of *priyayi*, of Javanese aristocrat, which he hates as a consequence of his introduction to the egalitarian and humanistic teachings of the French Revolution he learns at school.

At this point of his character development, Minke seems to see the Javanese culture and the European ideals as two rigidly separated entities. One is traditional, feudal, patriarchal, and humiliating, while the other is modern, egalitarian, fraternal, and liberating. One is the culture he really wants to depart; the other is the one he desires to fully embrace. Although it is a hard fact that the Javanese culture and the European ideals are, by definition, different and separated, it is also true that the two may reside in one person. This kind of awareness escapes Minke. For Minke at this stage, there is no possibility of the gray area, or the space in between the two, even though he himself in fact occupies that area or space. At this point which precedes his profound association and learning about the fact of the colonial oppression from his informal teachers like Nyai Ontosoroh, Kammer, Ter Haar, and Khouw Ah Soe, Minke seems to be still unaware of the complexity of his own identity. In short, Minke of the first book of the Buru Quartet has not recognized yet that he is a hybrid. The second book, *Child of All Nations*, describes how Minke come to the realization of his “true” identity.

How does Minke learn about his hybrid identity? And how does he react toward this realization? First of all, it must be stated that Minke does not learn about his hybridity at school. In this colonial institution, what he learns is only how to adore European modernity from afar and desires for it while at the same time despise his own inherited culture. In short, Minke does not come to a realization that he is hybrid with the help of his teachers. This fact can be seen in his initial impression of Nyai Ontosoroh when they meet each other in person for the first time. At this moment, Minke describes Nyai as a strange appearance: “A *native* woman entered, wearing a traditional Javanese wrap *skirt and a white blouse* embellished with expensive lace ... *Her Dutch* was good, with correct school pronunciation” (Toer, 1990a: 29, italics added). Because he never learns about it at school, Minke has a difficult time reconciling the two seemingly contradictory realities: nativeness and Europeaness in one person. (He is not even aware that he himself has also been a place of such contradiction.) Minke admits that he is lost in understanding Nyai: “The people and everything around her were indeed in her grip, and I, myself, too. From what school had she graduated that she appeared so educated, intelligent? ... And if she did graduated from a school, how was she able to accept her situation as a nyai? I couldn’t understand any of this” (Toer, 1990a: 49).

For Minke, Nyai is like a person from a different universe. Before this native woman, Minke can but question his previous naïve belief that everything that comes from West or Europe is great and good and that Javanese is a total failure and defeat. “Indeed, this was no ordinary nyai. She faced me, an H.B.S. student, without any feeling of

inferiority. She had the courage to state her opinion. She was aware of her own strength of character” (Toer, 1990a: 70). Nyai’s presence opens Minke’s eyes of the possibility of the crisscrossing of two cultures in one person and that crisscrossing does not necessarily mean bad, as Nyai is indeed admirable.

But, despite those great—supposedly European—qualities, what is Nyai Ontosoroh but a woman who was once—when she was young—forcefully sold by her own parents to a Dutch official who then made her his concubine? Nyai is a perfect example of the banished person. She was uprooted from her own safety, exiled from her own home. After that she had to live with a foreigner in a foreign house. But, she refused to give in. Coming from a Javanese background, just like Minke, she determined to learn modern knowledge from his master. She learned Dutch; she learned how to run a business; she learned how to have dignity in front of others both natives and Europeans. What she finally becomes is a hybrid person. And like Minke who, as we have mentioned earlier in this chapter, does not think that he still has a real name, Nyai, too, lost her real name. Narrating her own life story as a lullaby to her daughter, Nyai says, “As soon as I regained consciousness, I knew I was no longer the Sanikem [Nyai’s maiden, Javanese name] of the previous day. ... And the name Sanikem disappear forever” (Toer, 1990a: 87).

I believe that Pramoedya, as the author of *Buru Quartet*, has intentionally put the events of Minke’s life in such a neat sequence so that we, as the readers, can see the almost linear progress of his character maturity or development. That is another reason to see the *Buru Quartet* as a *bildungsroman*. So, following the introduction of the character Nyai

Ontosoroh who helps open Minke's eyes that there is a possibility of a gray, or hybrid, or crisscrossing area between Javanese and European cultures, for example, Minke is now more mature and equipped to see the ambivalence of his own identity.

Now being aware of his own hybridity, Minke's attitude toward (his old) Javanese identity, as we can see, turns out to be more complex to simply be contained in one simple term like contempt or dissatisfaction or unhappiness or detest or disgust. The Javanese identity alone presents to Minke something problematic. This identity is not only embodied or represented by his patriarchal, feudalistic, and rank-oriented father and brother, which, as already been mentioned several times earlier, Minke is clearly unhappy about. The Javanese identity also presents itself to Minke in his loving and accepting mother. Minke always feels like he is at home whenever he meets his mother, the side of Javanese culture that lulls him. In a passage from the first book when Minke is musing over his longing for his mother in nostalgic way, we can clearly see how he is attached to this "mother":

"[M]y heart was seized so suddenly by this longing for my mother ... She lifted up my chin, looked into my face, as if I were a four-year-old child. And her soft, loving voice moved me. My eyes overflowed with tears. This was my mother, just as before, my own mother. ... She took a breath and stroked my cheek as if I were a baby. ... Mother didn't fault me. I did not have to deny anything ... When I was a little boy, I used to tell her excitedly about what my schoolteachers had said. This time too. About Miss Magda Peters, whose stories were so interesting, about the French Revolution, its meaning, its basic principles. Mother only laughed, not refuting anything. Just when I was a little child" (Toer, 1990a: 128).

But, just as Minke has left his father and brother, who represent the side of the Javanese culture he is unhappy about, Minke, too, has departed from his mother—that loving and

lulling representation of the Javanese identity. Both of these departures are an irreversible and irrevocable journey, no matter if the first is a voluntary departure and the second is not.

Seen from his now hybrid position, Minke's longing of ever coming "home" to his mother is like an infantile desire, a nostalgic remembering of the better, glorious day of the past. Both Minke and his mother, however, recognize the fact that they can never be in the same realm again. About this impossibility, his mother says to Minke: "I will not obstruct you, and will not call you back. Travel along the road you hold to be best" (Toer, 1990a: 131). The best they can do is to admit this and, maybe, rather loosely practice what Wilbur Zelinsky following Herbert Gans suggests in *The Enigma of Ethnicity* (2001) as "symbolic ethnicity." Symbolic ethnicity refers to the final recognition of the impossibility to go back to whatever they perceived as their "original cultural home." The displaced people, who have been integrated into a new cultural (or ethnic) space, still optionally and part-timely choose to

"... [R]emember, cherish and honor the ancestral culture ... by consuming certain foods and beverages on certain occasions, using a few pungent words or phrases from an otherwise forgotten language, simulating traditional practices during culturally resonant holidays, festivals, and ceremonies, ..." (52).

This way, in an almost apologetic manner to his beloved mother, Minke expresses his still somehow clinging-on to the mother's cultural identity: "I still remember, Mother. I still read the Javanese books" (Toer, 1990a: 130). And Minke also takes a bit pride when he is

adorned with “a true Javanese costume” for his father’s inauguration ceremony, although right after then he is aware that this is, too, that dashing clothes and appearance of his is a “products of mankind’s earth at the end of the nineteenth century” (Toer, 1990a: 133). In short, Minke and his mother come to a sad realization that *there is no real coming-home, because home no longer exists*. What left is fragments of memories they can symbolically revisit now and then and a sentimental longing of ever going back.

The Story of a Brown Dutchman

Just as the invention of the name “Minke” is a curious case, so is Minke’s other famous epitaph “Brown Dutchman.” If the name “Minke” comes from the mouth of his teacher, it is Minke’s mother who for the first time speaks of the term “Brown Dutchman.” Both of the names are pejorative, and they are spoken to Minke by two most venerated and respected figures of his life. The name “Minke,” as we have discussed, is a degrading nickname by making fun of the standard English, so that it can be read as the subtle and yet formidable act of preventing Minke from joining the proper European or Western circle as he might desire. It is simply another way of saying just like what Herman Mellema, Nyai’s master, says to Minke: “You think ... because you wear European clothes, mix with Europeans, and can speak a little Dutch you then become a European? You are still a monkey” (Toer, 1990a: 47). With inventing the name “Minke,” the teacher and master

otherize Minke. He does not belong to their group and will never be one. Our question is whether the same mode of exclusion or banishment is happening with his calling “Brown Dutchman”? Why is this wicked phrase put on Minke’s mother’s lips, the representation of the Javanese culture that he may want to maintain?

Minke’s mother speaks out the phrase, I will argue, first of all to lovingly mock Minke in regards to his run away or infidelity to his inherited, traditional cultural identity. The mother with that phrase mocks Minke’s conscious choice to depart from the Javanese identity and, to a certain degree, his being hybrid. Minke’s being hybrid means that he is no longer “purely” Javanese. As said by the mother, a truly Javanese person “... pays heed to those older, those with greater right to your respect, those who have more power,” (Toer, 1990a: 130) while Minke seems to challenge all those characteristics his mother believes to be uniquely Javanese. Minke does not think twice to challenge those characterizations especially when he sees the paternalistic and feudalistic patterns that he hates so much in the Javanese culture.

The phrase “Brown Dutchman” also suggests how Minke’s mother is suspicious and probably worried that her son has become someone she does not recognize anymore, which is somehow true. But, her mother goes further, suspecting that Minke has turned himself into a Dutch—the colonizer, the infidel, the “savage” in her Javanese sense. Minke is indeed no more Javanese in that sense. “You’re [Minke] indeed no longer Javanese. Educated by the Dutch, you’ve become Dutch, a brown Dutchman, acting this way. Perhaps you’ve become a Christian” (Toer, 1990a: 130).

The third way of interpreting the phrase “Brown Dutchman” is, I would argue, that it is more than a simple motherly gesture of concern for her prodigal son. Those sentences of Minke’s mother are like a whip that is stronger than a simple mock or suspicion. It acts like a verdict: that, yes, Minke is guilty for his being not a real Javanese anymore. Even though departing from the Javanese culture is an ambivalent thing for Minke, there are only a few things could potentially be worse or more serious for him than hearing the verdict of banishment from the mouth of the person he loves very much, the person dearest to his heart, the person he can feel free to regress to. His mother herself has banished Minke out of her “cultural house.” He must have left the home, and this experience, of course, raises and involves a deep feeling of loss of rootedness.

In the Lacanian sense, this experience or feeling of loss of “the perceived union with the mother” signifies the development or the movement of a child from the Imaginary Order to the Symbolic Order. If the Imaginary Order is characterized by the indescribable feeling of unity with the mother—where the sense of separated selfhood is not a matter since the child cannot articulate it for the lack of language—the Symbolic Order is signified by “the experience of separation from others, and the biggest separation is the separation from the intimate union we experienced with our mother” (Tyson, 2000: 27-28). And this feeling of loss now finds its way of articulation since in the Symbolic Order the child begins to appropriate language. Only through language can a child now articulate his or her feeling. The feeling of loss of the perceived union with the mother that Minke experiences here when his mother characterizes him as not having the quality of Javanese

anymore is, to me, fairly comparable to the experience of loss that an exile feels when he or she is banished or separated—either forcefully or voluntarily—from his or her motherland.

Exile, following Edward Said, is fundamentally a terrible experience whose essential sadness can never be surmounted. It is “the unhealable rift forced between a human being and a native place, between the self and its true home (Said, 1984: 137). In short, it is a discontinuous state of being because people in exile are people cut off from their roots, their past, and their original cultural identity. Even though most of the times the term “exile,” as just being mentioned, brings to our mind the imagery of people who are either forcefully or voluntarily displaced or banished from their land for ideological or political reasons like the Jews from the Old Testament, or the Palestinians and Armenians from the twentieth century, Minke shares the similar kind of feeling of loss of home with them. And, just like in the Lacanian sense where the separation with the mother constitutes a child’s most important experience of loss which will haunt him all his life, which will also then prompts him to seek for the substitutes great and small for that loss—termed as *objet petit a*—there is also “an urgent need to reconstitute their broken lives” in the exiled people (Said, 1984: 140). In Minke’s case, this effort to substitute what is lost has some turns. The first turn happens when he desires to participate in modernity.

Minke’s effort to substitute what he has lost by desiring modernity is comparable to the exile desires for home. Even though this seems futile, it is the faith that somehow there is a still connection between the self and its homeland that makes the experience of

uprooted bearable. Edward Said's anecdote about Faiz Ahmad Faiz, a Pakistani exiled poet, who suddenly felt very happy just by meeting Eqbal Ahmad, another Pakistani friend and a fellow exile, even though that encounter did not by any means freed him for his feeling of loss of the motherland or physically transported him back to Pakistan, is a very good example of how an act of recuperation is working by making the exile experience something livable. About this, Said writes, "What I watched required no translation: it was an enactment of a homecoming expressed through defiance and loss, as if to say 'Zia, we are here.' Of course Zia was the one who was really at home and who would not hear their exultant voices" (Said, 2000: 138).⁶

Minke's *objet petit a* for his feeling of loss is his desire of embrace the new, modern Western ideals. But Minke is neither able to fully recuperate the loss nor to arrive in the desired place, modernity. As for the first failure, it is clear in the previous suggestion that his departing from his old Javanese culture is a one-way, irreversible trip. And even if, hypothetically, Minke is able to arrive in the desired space, what is modernity but the age of anxiety and estrangement, a space spiritually orphaned and alienated (Said, 2000:139). From its early conception, modernity is deeply characterized by suspicion of the traditional values, of the domestic safety, of old systems of belief. About the emergence of modernity in the Western world, Edward Said writes: "Nietzsche taught us to feel uncomfortable with tradition, and Freud to regard domestic intimacy as the polite face painted on patricidal and incestuous rage" (2000: 139). So, whether Minke's decision to depart has a point of arrival

⁶ Zia here refers to General Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq, the sixth President of Pakistan from 1977 to 1988, who exiled Faiz Ahmad Faiz to Beirut, Lebanon.

or not, one thing is clear, it involves a deep feeling of loss comparable to the feeling of loss of the exiles.

For Minke, being a “Brown Dutchman” which means being hybrid—in the sense of both neither being totally Javanese nor fully Dutch and, at the same time, taking a bit of traditional Javanese and a bit of modern European—is therefore, not a position to be taken lightly. It is a burdensome situation. As we have discussed, being hybrid is comparable living in exile. And if living in exile is a lost situation, so is being a hybrid person. But, living in exile, with no real sense of rootedness to a particular idea of homeland or primary identity has become the main signifier of modernity itself. In other words, modernity, that Western concept which Minke learns at school and comes to adore, is an era born of and heavily signified by loss—loss of sense of home, loss of tradition, loss of domestic safety, loss of religion, and, in short, loss of “epic.” Being hybrid is on one hand a melancholic situation—a tragedy, according to Said. But there is also the other side of hybridity that empowers its subject to be more creative than those not having such an experience.

Chapter 3

Possibilities in Hybridity

Minke, the main character of the Buru Quartet, as we have discussed in chapter 2, is a hybrid person. He is hybrid because his new identity is a mix of Javanese culture and European ideals. Minke's identity becomes hybrid because he, who comes from and grows up in the Javanese cultural background, participates in the colonial education system, which then introduces him to ideas of modernity, including the ideals of the French Revolution and technological advancements in mass printing. In Minke, we can see the trace of the crisscrossing of the East and the West.

As a hybrid, Minke is neither a "pure" Javanese nor a "real" Dutch. By his mother, his hybridity is termed as "Brown Dutchman." Because of his hybridity, Minke must occupy a gray space, an area of unstable and flexible identity—an area lacks of fixity and stability of identity. This new space Minke inhabits is, as we have discussed in Chapter 2, heavily characterized by the feeling of loss of the rootedness, connectedness, or union with either Javanese or European identity. Living in this new space, therefore, also means living in a nervous, jealous condition. There is an insistent dream of ever coming home to the old identity, at least symbolically. At the same time, however, there is also a strong desire to arrive at the desired identity, which always escapes, slips away, anyway. Minke's feeling of loss can well be explained with Lacanian perspective. Following Lacan, the efforts to

recuperate the loss is comparable to the pursuits of *objet petit a*. *Objet petit a* itself can be understood as anything that, we think and we believe, will be able to replace the loss (Tyson, 2006: 28, 34). We think that if we are getting richer, if we have a faster sport car, if we have the latest cell-phone, and so on and so forth we will be happy. But as we have discussed, in Minke's case—as in any other case—the *objet petit a* can never replace what has lost. What has lost is lost forever, just like the loss of the Imaginary Order upon the dawn of the Symbolic Order in Lacanian perspective.

We have also discussed that living between identities the way Minke does is also comparable to living in exile. Indeed, Minke, one way or another, experiences being exiled himself. He is “exiled” from his old (Javanese) identity, first voluntarily through his going out from “home” to participate in the colonial education and later the exile experience comes more like banishment when his mother calls him a “Brown Dutchman,” suggesting his no longer a Javanese. Minke also experiences exile in its other senses: alienation and exclusion. This exilic experience happens when he is prevented from joining the European identity that he naively admires. The name Minke itself—suggesting his similarity with “monkey”—blocks his way from being a truly member of European society. We thus can say that Minke experiences a double exile: first from his old identity and then from his desired identity. How horrible that exilic experience is to Minke has been discussed in Chapter 2, using Edward Said's insight that suggests that exile is fundamentally a terrible experience whose essential sadness can never be surmounted. In short, Chapter 2 discusses how being hybrid is a downside experience nobody may want to live in, but it is an

unavoidable consequence for an educated native like Minke who has his legs straddled between two identities: the old traditional Javanese and the new modern Western cultures.

This chapter will explore what Minke's attitude is toward his becoming a hybrid person. By viewing Minke as the tragic hero of the *Buru Quartet*, it is actually not very difficult for us to assume that, using our common sense, he will not simply give in to all those downsides of the hybridity he experiences. And that is probably the case. The spirit to fight back—even when this spirit is always accompanied or haunted by the realization of the impossibility to win—is the underlying force that drives Minke to creatively make use of his hybridity to forge his own, unique space. The realization of the impossibility to win can be inferred from Minke's conversation with Nyai Ontosoroh, his mother-in-law, toward the end of the first book: “‘We have been defeated, Mama,’ I [Minke] whispered. ‘We fought back, child, Nyo, as well and honorably as possible’” (Toer, 1990a: 359). The similar sentiment is echoed by Said when he wrote: “The achievements of exile are permanently undermined by the loss of something left behind forever” (Said, 1984: 137). In that sense, no matter how successful an exile like Minke does in recuperating the loss, it will not completely replace what has lost. It will simply ease the pain, but the wound remains.

In discussing this “creative,” and possibly lighter, side of hybridity, I will still borrow a lot from the insights offered by Edward Said in his book *Reflections on Exile* (1984). Said mentions in this book that hybridity, for its subjects, creates a foreign situation that needs to be made sense of. This new and foreign situation prompts hybrid

people, or, in Said's words, exiles, to be creative. By proposing some excellent examples of creative exiles and borrowing Lukacs' idea about novel as the form of "transcendental homelessness," Said argues that hybridity is pregnant with creativity: "It is not surprising that so many exiles seem to be novelists, chess players, political activists, and intellectuals" (Said, 1984: 144). And Edward Said is himself an example of such creative thinker who at the same time, not accidentally though, is an exile.

In the discussion of the hybridity, I will also make use of Salman Rushdie's ideas as can be read in his book *Imaginary Homelands* (1992). Salman Rushdie, like Edward Said, is an "exile." He writes most of the times in Britain, far away from his parental homeland: India. Rushdie is one of few writers who are very positive in viewing hybridity. He does not really see the problem in the process of mongrelization, crisscrossing, and confusion of two or more identities or cultures. This concept of mongrelization will be discussed later on in this chapter. Rushdie argues that however ambiguous and shifting the space of hybridity may be, it is a fertile territory, which opens to rereading, interpretation, and recreation. Hybridity provides a new angle to see the reality, which is unlikely being seen in another way.

The Indian great writer by some is mistakenly seen as a dubious nationalist vis-à-vis Mahatma Gandhi, Sir Rabindranath Tagore (1861-1941) furthermore saw that there is no possibility of Indian nationalism, or any postcolonial nationalism for that matter, outside hybridity. For Tagore, India will not be a great country—it will even not be able to truly free itself from colonialism—if it sticks to two rigid reactions toward West:

unthinking deference and unthinking defiance. The hybridity, i.e. the space where the best of the East and of the West come together, is what will make India great. Hybridity, or in Tagore's sense more like open-mindedness to the best of one's own and others' cultures, is something to be embraced and strived for, instead of being avoided. But Tagore was vastly misunderstood. Many Indians, as can be read from the piece by Ramachandra, saw and still see his attitude as unpatriotic. But, that is the risk of being a hybrid, an "impure" people. The paradox is that it is in this hybrid space, this exile—where the acts of re-creating, re-imagining are possible—following Said, that nationalism initially grows up.

Hybridity as a Product of Modernity That Creates a Space

Edward Said, first of all, sees exile as a jealous state. As such, exile is a state between self and the others. It does not belong to either one. As neither part of "us" nor "them," exile has no real place in the binary structure of self-other. Exile might once be part of "us," but then, for some reasons, it is not any more. Exile is not part of "them" either because of their realization that they do not belong to "them." Exile is, therefore, also a non-belonging state. About this state, Edward Said writes, "And just beyond the frontier between 'us' and the 'outsiders' is the perilous territory of non-belonging" (Said, 1984: 140). Right after writing this, Said adds with another comment that it is in this non-belonging space that in the modern era immense aggregates of humanity loiters as refugees and displaced persons.

We may now want to question: Does, by saying this, Said want to suggest that exile is a particular problem of modernity? The answer can be both yes and no. Exile, either as a voluntary or forceful move out of one's perceived root or home, exists in each and every historical period. In the Old Testament, we learn how the Chosen People of Israel were exiled to Babylon. In history class, we might learn about Armenians who were driven out of their homeland, and maybe also about Chinese Indonesian who were brutally taken out from their homes in the 1998 riot. In addition to that, millions of people also moved out from their homelands to foreign places to get a better life, to avoid war, etc. These are only few examples of exilic movement. But the modern era, that's what I think what Edward Said wants to say, is an era where living in or even becoming exile becomes the only possible and logical result or consequence of its inherent spirit. What is modernity then?

One great way to see modern era is to understand it as a period of suspicion. In this era, people are pushed to question to its limit every convention and myth of the old tradition. There is no epic in modernity. No single interpretation stands without challenge or reinterpretation. Questioning and challenging are two strong words in modernity. The proponents of modernity were the pioneers in questioning and challenging general assumptions and beliefs. As Said writes: "Nietzsche taught us to feel uncomfortable with tradition, and Freud to regard domestic intimacy as the polite face painted on patricidal and incestuous rage" (Said, 1984: 137).

But with that spirit let ablaze, the consequence is the immense feeling of loss: loss of belief to whatever people used to believe, loss of rootedness to whatever people used to anchor themselves with and so on and so forth. This feeling of loss, or lack, becomes one of the core characteristics of modernity or modern era. One's introduction and immersion to the spirit of modernity makes him or her depart from his or her "home." With that, the person becomes an "orphan." As Said further says: "Modern period ... [is] spiritually orphaned and alienated, the age of anxiety and of estrangement" (Said, 1984: 137). Once the spirit of modernity touches someone, therefore, there is no other way for the person except to become an "exile" from his or her old self, tradition, identity, and culture. This non-belonging state is what then, in my opinion, pushes the person to become a hybrid, i.e. someone who takes a little bit of this and of that and synthesizes them into his or her own new "identity."

Furthermore, we also find that in modern era becoming an exile does not necessarily mean being sent away or uprooted from one's "physical" home or country. Being in exile, generally speaking, refers to the situation where someone is uprooted, separated from his/her tradition. In short, it is a situation that makes the person culturally homeless. And since "cultural" alienation, estrangement, and orphanhood—in short, the feeling of loss—is the logical result of living in modern world, it can be assumed then that anyone who has been touched or introduced to modernity will, like it or not, also live in exile, at least culturally, if not also physically.

Our main character, Minke, is an admirer of modernity. He is a child and student of modernity. Thus Minke, as we can read from the *Buru Quartet*, cannot escape from the gloomy consequence of modernity. When, as we have discussed in Chapter 2, he questions his tradition, expresses his suspicion over the old inherited values, challenges his father and his brother, and especially when he must live with the disappointment because his mother banishes him by stating his becoming a “Brown Dutchman” (Toer, 1990a: 121-125), Minke experiences how his introduction to modernity and desire to embrace it means that he must bear the consequences: the feeling of loss, the experience of exile, and the estrangement. But, given his time and place and especially the stage of his character development, we can assume that he sees modernity, at least initially, in its optimistic and sweet sense. At school, modernity is not presented and introduced to him as a force that can undermine his old fixed identity (or identities) as it really does. It is not advertised to him along with its gloomy prospect. Minke only knows that he just needs to desire and embrace modernity and he will experience “heaven.” Modernity comes to him as a “trendy” word. It is a term he admits to himself he has not yet had a complete understanding about but which brings him a promise whose sweetness is beyond imagination. Minke shares optimism toward modernity with his European teachers when he says:

“Machines will replace all and every kind of work. People will have nothing to do except enjoy themselves. You are fortunate indeed, my students, he said, to be able to witness the beginning of the modern era here in the Indies. Modern! How quickly that word had surged forward and multiplied itself like bacteria throughout the world ... even though I still don’t fully understand its meaning” (Toer, 1990a: 18).

Here, we read how the young Minke interprets modernity. He only views modernity through one aspect of its manifestations, i.e. the technological advancement it produces that many believe will make human beings' lives easier and more efficient. Modernity is, for Minke at this stage, understood as nothing more than or different from its positive manifestations. But to us, outside observers, it is clear as daylight that those manifestations of modernity Minke admire are an incomplete picture of modernity itself. In other words, those manifestations do not reflect modernity in its wholeness. In the Lacanian sense, for Minke at this stage, the *objet petit a* of modernity—if I may say so—is misunderstood as the Reality that has lost itself. The ever-suspicious nature of modernity as mentioned above has not yet caught the young Minke's attention. It is only when Minke finally realizes how he has become hybrid, becomes a "Brown Dutchman," that he properly sees how he has changed so significantly from the old Minke he used to know. And only at this stage does he realize that he has become an "orphan" who had irrevocably lost something very important: his old identity.

As a product or logical consequence of modernity or living in modern era, hybridity, as well as becoming exile, loosely following Lukacs, can be viewed as the situation of cultural homelessness. The situation of cultural homelessness itself suggests a cut off from the cultural roots, the motherland, and the past. Modernity has thus "separated the children from their mothers." The situation is probably like novel that lacks of epic experience. What is left is only information and not advice of life. Such homelessness

needs to be transcended. There must be another home one want to arrive. When this is impossible, the transcending efforts can take form as an enterprise of recreating or even of (re)imagining of home. Otherwise, hybridity or exile will only be an unbearable depressing situation.

The world of exile—and of hybridity—is, according to Edward Said, also the world of estrangement; it “... is unnatural and its reality resembles fiction” (Said, 1984: 144).

Exile is unnatural because it lacks of the sense of naturalness of a home. Becoming exile or becoming hybrid makes someone feels that he lives in other world, unfamiliar setting. It is like living someone else’s life. What can one do in such a world or situation? When being encountered with something unnatural, people tend to avoid it, or when it is unavoidable as in case of hybridity or exile for those encountering modernity, they need to make it looks somehow natural and acceptable. It is just natural that people always want to make sense of things. Maybe, in the end they cannot make all things “normal” to them but what they need is making sure that as many as possible things understandable.

These efforts, either viewed as transcending one’s cultural homelessness or understanding and reinterpreting the unnaturalness of exilic place, are, however futile, representing the common strategies exiles or hybrid people take to bear the burden of the ultimate feeling of loss they suffer. In fact, transcending that feeling of cultural homelessness is, according to Edward Said, probably one positive possibility of living in exile and becoming hybrid. Hybridity does not only means the rise of the feeling of loss. It also refers to the space it creates that enables the hybrid persons or the exiles to be creative

in recreating or reimagining their own places. In line with that notion, Said furthermore suggests that there might be a possibility of “pleasures of exile, ... some positive things to be said for a few of its conditions. Seeing ‘the entire world as a foreign land’ makes possible originality of vision” (Said, 1984: 148). This means that being a hybrid person, or being in an exile, does not only comprise of a depressing situation in regards to the state of non-belonging but it also offers opportunity to recreate the “world.” In existentialistic sense, being hybrid endows us with freedom to make or remake ourselves. This can be daunting prospect because freedom implies great responsibility. But the open space that exile or hybridity offers is too invaluable to simply be ignored.

The hybrid, exilic world that Minke occupies following his “banishment” from his parental cultural identity and the experience of rejection from his European teachers can also be viewed as a space of homelessness that needs to be transcended and reinterpreted. This new world of his does not only represent his loss of his old world or worlds but also offers him with a wide space to review his own existence and function in the society of mankind as well as to revision and reorient his life. There is a specific moment in the second book of the Buru Quartet, *Child of All Nations*, where Minke describes his activities following the death of his wife. (The event of the death of his wife itself functions like the culmination of Minke’s loss of “complete” belief in European ideals with which he once desires to unite. The anguish resulted from this experience is in every sense comparable of his feeling of loss when his mother calls him a “Brown Dutchman.”) Those activities give us hints about the possibility offered by Minke’s hybridity as well as his

willingness and capacity to use that space to recreate something new and to understand the world and its problems from a different perspective.

“Life went on without Annelies [Minke’s wife]. I returned to my ... activities: reading papers and certain magazines, books, and letters; writing notes and articles ... All this reading taught me a great deal about myself, about my place in my environment, in the world at large, and in the unrelenting march of time. Looking at myself this way, I felt I was being carried along by the wind, with no place on earth where I could stand secure” (Toer, 1990b: 47).

Minke’s ability to deal with and transcend his feelings of loss and sees the possibility in his hybridity does not come at once. Just as his coming to the realization that his identity is hybrid happens gradually—step by step—so does his capability to recreate something new out of that hybridity. The narration of the *Buru Quartet* describes how Minke struggles on daily basis to transcend his deep feelings of loss. It is described like an on-going *bildungsroman*. Minke’s character is narrated as going through the process of maturing, with achievements as well as failures. In short, Minke’s efforts to recreate something out of his hybridity or to make use of the open space that the hybridity offers is, following the notion introduced by Stuart Hall when referring to the creation of cultural identity, something “in becoming.” It is an organic, dynamic process, and maybe also a never-ending one.

Now, how does Minke transcend his feelings of cultural homelessness, his feeling of loss? And, in what way or ways do his hybridity propel him to reevaluate, recreate, and re-imagine his place in this earth of mankind? Just like Edward Said, Salman Rushdie,

James Joyce, Walter Benjamin, V.S. Naipaul, and many other exilic figures who embody George Steiner's thesis, quoted in Said's *Reflection on Exile*, that "a whole genre of the twentieth-century Western literature is 'extraterritorial,' a literature by and about exiles, symbolizing the age of the refugee," (Said, 1984:137)—confirming Said's thesis that modern Western culture is in large part the work of exiles, émigrés, and refugees, to which I will add hybrid people—chose to be writers, so does Minke. Minke makes an early and conscious decision to become a writer. How he struggles to become a hybrid writer will be clear later on in this and the next chapters.

Minke realizes that the best way for him to transcend the experience or feeling of cultural homelessness resulted from his introduction to modernity is not by becoming a tool of colonialism like his father and brother. He does not want to become a bupati, or any other bureaucrat in the colonial government. He wants to be a writer. And it is not enough for him to simply become a writer, because he wants to write things about humanity, about the struggle of the oppressed against the oppressor, following the trod of his favorite writer, Multatuli. Minke's determination to become a writer who writes about human's life and its problems can be inferred from the strong statement he shouts out loud to his feudalistic, rank-oriented brother when they meet in their parents' house at the night prior to their father's inauguration as a bupati:

Indeed the civil service reports were something that never attracted my interest: appointments, dismissals, transfers, pensions. Nothing to do with me. The world of priyayi, Javanese aristocrats who became administrators for the Dutch colonial bureaucracy, was not my world. Who cared if the devil was appointed smallpox official or was sacked dishonorably because of embezzlement? My world was not

rank and position, wages, and embezzlement. My world was this earth of mankind and its problem” (Toer, 1990a: 125).

In fact, one of Minke’s early subjects of observation for writing is the rise of Japan as a new world power. About this choice, he writes: “Perhaps, in all of the Indies, I am the one and only Native who keeps notes like these. Who else is interested in other peoples? Notes like these bring no respect, let alone any material benefit” (Toer, 1990b: 49). Useless and valueless are his early writings seem to be, it is actually through this observation and writing about the Japanese, and later also about the Chinese, the Filipino, and other colonized people that Minke learns about his own people’s suffering under the Dutch colonialism. His short but fateful friendship with Khouw Ah Soe, a nationalist Chinese who comes all the way from China mainland to the Indies to raise the awareness among his fellow Chinese about their own petty-mindedness, has prompted Minke to raise the same question: what have I done to help my own people in their struggle against Western colonialism?

Thus Minke does not choose to write about the lives of the big shots, either Dutch or Javanese. He does not write about the affairs of a resident or a bupati, or even the Governor General of the Indies or any local king. Minke, we can say, does not only make a conscious choice to write but also to write about common people, about humanity in general. Why so? Why does Minke opt to write about these people? Since Minke, as have been suggested several times, is a child of European humanism and an big admirer of French Revolution’s spirit, it is actually not that difficult to see why he wants to write

about the lives of common people. He wants to bring that spirit alive. But, I also believe that there must be something more than that “objective” reason for the choice of the subject of his writing. I am talking here about a more personal reason to Minke.

Maybe we can start with quoting what Nyai Ontosoroh says to Minke about writing about common people: “Millions upon millions of people suffer silently, like the river stones. You, Child, must at least be able to shout. Do you know why I love you above all others? Because you write. Your voice will not be silenced and swallowed up by the wind; it will be eternal, reaching far, far into the future” (Toer, 1990b: 83). The common people, in this case the oppressed natives of the East Indies colony, are the people who have no say in the making of the colonial policy, which somehow determine their fates and their wellbeing. They are the group of people who are lost in the colonial structure of power. This situation which Nyai Ontosoroh describes as “suffer silently” and which I will generally characterize as “non-existent” or voiceless is to some points comparable to the state of non-belonging Minke experiences as a hybrid person in the binary structure of identity. As a hybrid person, Minke wants to transcend his cultural homelessness, his loss. He wants to forge a new space for himself. He wants his voice heard. Hypothetically, in the spirit of selfish altruism, Minke feels “emphatic” with what his fellow natives must suffer under the Dutch colonialism and wants to help them transcending their own situation, too.

Besides, Minke also wants to prove that the accusation made by his two close friends, Jean Marais and Kommer, that he does not care or know his own people are not

true at all. Minke, therefore, takes a great pride of himself when he is finally able to finish his writing pieces about the lives of Surati and Trunodongso, two common people he meets when he takes a vacation in the village:

“In my bag were two manuscripts. ... Both contained eternal values, both were dedicated to eternity. ... The world must be told how Java’s farmers are being thrown off their rice lands ... by the sugar factories, and with the aid of the Native civil servants in colonial employ and of the village officials. If Multatuli had been here in Surabaya, I would have come to him and said: Teacher, today I begin to follow where you have trod before. Today I am important” (Toer, 1990b: 190).

I will also argue that Minke, here echoing Pramoedya’s belief, totally buys into the realist socialism idea that writing is not just a means towards self-satisfaction. Writing must be a way of giving substance to our lives. For Minke, as for Pramoedya, art is not just for the art’s sake. That is why he writes about the oppressed that are bereaved of their rights by the colonialism. That is why he writes about people like Trunodongso and Surati. That is why he wants to publish them no matter what is the risk for him personally. Minke’s writings about common people’s struggles, therefore, have twofold functions. In personal level, he does it to transcend his own experience of cultural homeless—he needs to create his own space, his unique place in the world. And, in social level, i.e. for the people that become the subjects of his writings, he wants to make sure that their voices be heard, their stories revealed.

Minke’s hybrid or exilic situation, to follow Salman Rushdie, also significantly influences the way he writes and the subject of his writing. It gives him a distinctive, fresh

perspective in viewing and understanding an event, a situation, a certain group of people, or any other things related to his subject of writing. If he was not a hybrid person, I believe he will not write the way he writes. In his writing, Minke does not simply record an event. What he writes is a story, a real people's story. Inside of it, Minke also subtly incorporates his own "opinion" and comment in regards to that story. In short, he does not feel hesitant at all to take side in the course of the story. Minke, as we may assume, takes side to the common people's case. His voice is echoed and reechoed here and there. He even makes self-reflection based on the story he writes.

As a writer, Minke neither becomes a historian nor a social scientist. He becomes a man of letters who reinterprets, reflects, and even recreates and invents things or stories. His hybrid situation, however difficult this position can be, has somehow liberated and enabled Minke to be creative and invent new things. Minke's hybridity liberates him from any expectation and rigidity of fixed genre. He does not have to write a Javanese song with all its formal requirements; he does not have to create a detailed and "objective" historical or demographic record as required by Western scientific standard. He does not pretend to write an accountable and objective history because "[h]istory is always ambiguous. Facts are hard to establish, and capable of being given many meanings. Reality is built on our prejudices, misconceptions and ignorance as well as on our perceptiveness and knowledge" (Rushdie, 1992: 25). In short, Minke does not become a (social) scientist. He becomes a "novelist," an "occupation" particular to hybrid, exilic writers like him who has been introduced to modernity.

Hybridity: East Meets West

From our discussion, we may infer that hybridity can basically be understood as the cultural situation of mixing, mongrelization, crisscrossing of two or more cultures in one space, both in its temporal and spatial senses. Minke, our main character, is an example of hybridity. He is hybrid because his new identity, both temporally and spatially, is the result of mixing, mongrelization, and crisscrossing of the Javanese and European or identities. As a hybrid, Minke's identity is "impure," and characterized by the feeling of cultural loss or homelessness. But as Minke transcends the feeling, his hybridity also opens up for him a space to be creative. With that space, Minke is able to recreate, reorient, and invent his own—in existentialistic term—"essence" in this earth of mankind. In this sense, hybridity gives Minke a choice not to simply comply with the already existing modes of identification.

This aspect of (personal, and later also social and political) choice hybridity offers adds up to its positive, upside features. The willingness and ability to use this choice is also what, for instance, Rabindranath Tagore suggests when he talks about what to do to make India a true "modern" state. Conceived as a modern state by its founding figures, India was also born out of the feeling of loss of cultural home. India of the "glorious" past did not exist anymore with the coming of European colonialism. But India could not simply embrace Western's ideals, too. India is a case of colonial hybridity. As a hybrid nation, India has and must make use of the choice to imagine its own new space. What can India do? First of all, India, according to Tagore, should not fall into two false attitudes or

reactions toward West: either unthinking deference or unthinking reference, either fear or flattery, either “passively dormant, or feebly imitating the West” (Ramachandra, Website: xix).

India, Tagore further suggests, must be able to truly and sincerely embrace its hybrid nature. Unable to do so will only mean that India denies its own “core” identity as a nation that was conceived upon and born out of spirit of modernity. To embrace its hybridity, India could and should choose a third way: “to embrace the best of the West without damage to her cultural traditions” (Ramachandra, Website: xix). The choice is, therefore, manifested in the conscious action of taking the chance of being “impure,” being a mongrelized people, living as “exiles” outside of the old identities—both East and West. Tagore, with this, is critical in seeing Indian nationalism. For him, Indian nationalism should not close its door to new ideas, from any directions they may come. India must then sort them out to find the best of each. Tagore sees that the staggering heterogeneity of India was the product of its hospitality, in the past, to cultures and ideas from outside.

“He wished that this openness be retained and even enhanced in the present. Unlike other patriots, Tagore refused to privilege a particular aspect of India—Hindu, North India, upper caste, etc.—and make this the essence of the nation, and then demand that other aspects conform or subordinate themselves to it. For Tagore, as the historian Tanika Sarkar has pointed out India ‘was and must remain land without a center’” (Ramachandra, Website: 1).

India, the hybrid nation, is in Tagore’s eyes, a mix and *mélange*, which has no single essence. In a more metaphysical way, Tagore explains how there is no nation, culture,

ideology or religious tradition can monopolize truth. All systems were a mixture of good and evil, of truth and untruth. “The only way to make one’s nation or culture less false was to broaden it by listening to (and learning from) other nations and cultures ... [India should] ‘choose the difficult middle path,’ resisting the easy options of an enthusiastic embrace of modernity or the uncritical return to tradition” (Ramachandra, Website: lvii, lix).

What about Minke? Like India as dreamed by Tagore, Minke, as we have mentioned again and again, is a space where hybridity finds its space. He starts with his non-belonging state. Through his personal struggles, Minke then comes to the realization of his hybridity—that his non-belonging state also means that he is a mix of the Javanese and Western cultures and identities—and a conscious decision to use that space to create and invent his own “essence.” He writes—critically—about humanity issues. He employs his writing skill and perspectives he learns from his European teacher. And he uses his activities of writing as well as dedicates his writings to “know his own people.” In Minke, the best, or at least the better part, of East and West meet and get synchronized. Where will this synchronization lead and how Minke’s story and *bildungsroman* can be seen as the metonymy of Indonesian nationalism will be discussed in the next and last chapter of this thesis.

Chapter 4

Problematizing Indonesia

'[I]ntimate tyranny' is the very stuff of which society . . . is constituted . . . There is no better sign of this intimate tyranny that makes society possible than 'language', or the symbolic, the originary (sic) tyranny par excellence, a regime of violence we escape (?) only in death.'

(Olaniyan in Heryanto, 2006:1)

In the previous chapters, we have discussed how Minke's character develops and matures. It all starts from his being a naïve young man who leaves his parental home. Prior to the event that I will call as his cultural departure, this young man, Minke, has been a member of the Javanese community—one of hundreds of ethnic groups that comprises Indonesia today. The Javanese community, as any other community for that matter, always makes an effort of self-identification. It is always in need to self-position itself in the bigger world. Putting these processes of self-identification and self-positioning in the binary structure of identity, the members of the Javanese community identify themselves, as we might assume, as occupying the position of “the self” vis-à-vis the Dutch community whom they see as occupying the position of “the other.” In the colonial setting, the Javanese community views itself as the oppressed, exploited, and colonized group of people while the Dutch as the oppressor, exploiter, and colonizer. The first is the “slave” while the latter is the master. They are completely different—as black and white—and there is very slight likeliness of “bridging” the two as well as probability of the existence of something in-between.

However, an almost unprecedented thing happened at the turn of the twentieth century that changed that stable scene. We have discussed in Chapter 1 that with the opening of access to Western-style education for a limited number of the Indonesian natives as the result of the Ethical policy, Minke, as a representation of the colonized, can now go to and study at school run by the colonizer, sitting in the same classroom and mixing with European and mixed-blood students. From the Javanese's perspective, this young man can be seen as departing from the realm of "the self" to study with and from "the other." To a certain degree, his departure is also to be seen as embracing the otherness. At school, young Minke indeed learns European knowledge and is introduced, among others, to modernity and humanity ideals. He is deeply fascinated by those ideals and, at some point, may desire to embrace them wholly at the cost of abandoning his parental identity. Yet, the deeper we explore into Minke's psychological world the clearer it is to us that Minke's character cannot rigidly be characterized by the full-embrace of a new cultural identity and the total loss of the old cultural identity. It is impossible for Minke to fully depart from his Javanese identity in order to wholly immerse into the European modernity. This impossibility is what makes Minke must deal with the new state of non-belonging, a state that we have seen is comparable to the situation of exile. Minke is no longer a Javanese but he is not a Dutch either. He is a "brown Dutchman," a hybrid whose identity is the mix, the crisscrossing, and the result of the process of mongrelization of the Javanese and the European values and cultures. Minke's hybrid identity is heavily characterized by the feeling of loss of the perceived rootedness and union with a fixed and

stable identity, either Javanese or European, and by efforts to recuperate or compensate the loss.

On the other hands, as we have discussed in Chapter 3, his hybridity also offers Minke with an opportunity to study his real situation from a distance and, as a consequence of it, a choice to revise, reorient, recreate, and even invent his own self or space. Along this line, Minke chooses to write. Moreover, he chooses to write about his own people. He uses the skill and humanistic perspective he learns at the Dutch school to help making the voice of his fellow oppressed natives heard. With his writings being widely read, Minke builds his readership around the solidarity sense to the oppressed. From that solidarity, he organizes people—not firstly and primarily based on old, primordial bonding like race or familial background although Minke still uses religion, in this case Islam, when he founds his first modern organization, SDI, but on the basis of the principle of modern organization. And since modern organization has no precedence in Indonesian history, Minke’s work can be seen as a pioneering project of imagining modern Indonesia in its embryonic stage.

This chapter, building upon the discussion of the previous chapters, will explore how Minke’s choice to write in Malay can be seen as the representation of Indonesia-in-the-making. In other words, we will be exploring how Minke’s character development up to his choice to use Malay as his language of writing and organizing people as portrayed in the *Buru Quartet* is the metonymy of the Indonesian *bildungsroman*. We may want to ask why Malay? And why does Minke choose to write in “market” Malay and not in official

Malay as expected by the Dutch colonizer? Malay itself is a vernacular originally spoken by a small group of people living in the east coast of Sumatra, Malay Peninsula, and west coast of Kalimantan. It has become the lingua franca for the trade activities in what today comprises Indonesia since centuries before European set their feet in the colony. Malay is, therefore, the language foreign to both the Dutch and Minke who happens to speak Javanese and Dutch. None of them can claim that it is them who have an exclusive ownership over Malay and that the other only borrow it. Both have no authority over the tongue. Malay is a language exterior to all, a language of in-betweenness according to James T. Siegel (1997: 32) who also suggests:

“Melayu [another word for Malay] is the language without authority, everyone speaks it, everyone negotiates meanings. Melayu was thus a language without the built-in authority the taking on of which gives one not only a sense of mastery but, as a speaker, the reassurance of having a place in the world” (16).

In a Lacanian sense, Minke’s decision to start writing in “market” Malay and stop writing in Dutch or Javanese (the latter he actually never does) clearly signifies his real departure from his Imaginary Order—where subjectivity is out of question and where he still feels completely “united” with either Javanese or European cultural “mothers”—to his Symbolic Order, which is characterized by the acquisition of a “new” language. This decision is consciously made regardless of Minke’s own skepticism over the ability of that particular tongue to properly express his inner world as well as to represent the reality. In the beginning, Minke—when being pressed by his two close friends, Jean Marais and Kommer—to start writing in Malay so that more natives will become among of his readers,

explicitly shows his reluctance. He says: “What can you say in Malay? An impoverished language like that? Riddled with borrowed words from every country in the world?” (Toer, 1990b: 109). He even feels suspicious that writing in Malay will only harm his own reputation: “He [Jean Marais] wanted me to write in Malay so that he himself could read my writings directly, while destroying my fame and achievement and prestige ... [M]y character, my individuality, could not be separated from the Dutch language. To separate these things would only make this person named Minke nothing better than roadside rubbish” (Toer, 1990b: 58). But in the end, he realizes and admits that he should write in market Malay if he really wants to reach his own people and makes their voices heard. There is no other way in his deposit.

In the Symbolic Order, Minke who has lost his old inherited and aspired languages (Javanese and Dutch languages, respectively) choose to make use a new tool or language. It is with this language that he works his subjectivity and builds his own opinion and say. These he does all the while he is aware of how limited, unstable, and poor that new language is. With the language he appropriates in the Symbolic Order, Minke invents his own space.

And if the story of Minke—from the moment he leaves his parental home to the time when he discovers Malay as the language of his writing—can be understood as the metonymy for Indonesian nationalism’s *bildungsroman*, we then understand how the Indonesian nationalism is, as Minke himself, something organic, dynamic, incomplete, and “in the making.” As such, Indonesia, as represented by Minke’s character development,

can be seen more as a project of what the future should look like, rather than a reality whose existence has already been there from the time immemorial. It is these dynamic characteristics of Indonesian nationalism that Pramoedya saw had been somehow denied and forcefully suppressed by Indonesian postcolonial regimes, especially under Suharto era (1966-1998). The story of Indonesia is the story of Minke and of Malay in the making. The rigid standardization of Indonesian language, the cooptation of the state toward the language, the creation and enforcement of the language of truth, and the denial of other utterances inside and outside the official “national language” creates a subtle and yet fascistic tyranny that Pramoedya, through his writings, wanted to challenge. Suhartoism, we may want to call it this way, with all its centralistic, paternalistic, and silencing policies deny the very “essence” of Indonesia, if such a thing exists at all.

In discussing the issue of Indonesian nationalism and the possibility of seeing Pramoedya’s Minke as its metonymy, I find the ideas proposed in Benedict Anderson’s *Imagined Community* (1991), Pheng Cheah’s *Spectral Nationality: Passages of Freedom from Kant to Postcolonial Literatures of Liberation* (2003), Henk Maier’s “Stammer and the Creaking Door: The Malay Writings of Pramoedya Ananta Toer,” (2002)⁷ and James T. Siegel’s *Fetish, Recognition, Revolution* (1997) very insightful. The first two thinkers mentioned above deeply engage in the discussion on the issue of nationalism in their respective works. Both see nationalism as a modern invention. Both agree with what Gellner suggests that “Nationalism is not the awakening of nations to self-consciousness: it

⁷ Maier’s paper can be found in Keith Foulcher and Tony Day (Eds.). *Clearing A Space: Postcolonial Readings of Modern Indonesian Literature*. Leiden, NL: KITLV Press. 2002.

invents nations where they do not exist” (Anderson, 1991: 6). But, if, to my reading, Anderson seems to be more historical in exploring the birth of the nation, suggesting nation as a cultural artifact of a particular kind so that to “understand them [sic] properly we need to consider carefully how they have come into historical being” (Anderson, 1991: 4), Cheah sounds to be more “metaphysical and positive” in his discussion on the project of nationalism. Cheah emphasizes the organic nature of nationalism as he writes: “This alleged organic power of origination is intimated by the nation’s etymological link to ‘nativity’ and ‘natality’” (Cheah, 2003: 1).

Benedict Anderson, who seems to me as departing from a Marxist point of view in his analysis of the nation, is very critical toward the idea of nationalism in general. He famously defines nation as an imagined political community that lacks of philosophy and, therefore, also of essence (Anderson, 1991: 6-7) and that its invention cannot be separated from the growth of world capitalism, in this case print-capitalism. Nationalism is, according to Anderson, a discourse whose existence is never neutral. The idea of nationalism functions like an ideology and the nation is invented at the first place to satisfy the capitalistic interests of its inventors and proponents. On the other hands, our second thinker and writer, Pheng Cheah, while admitting the lack of philosophical ground of nationalism when he writes: “Nationalism’s philosophical structure is not to be found in the thought or work of any particular philosopher, but in constellations of concepts that are necessary ... condition of nationality ... ‘freedom,’ ‘culture,’ and ‘organic life’” (Cheah, 2003: 4), sees that nationalism can also function as “the imagistic and specular dimension

of culture qua self-recursive mediating device ... associated with the organism as a self-perpetuating being” (Cheah, 2003: 235). Nation is an organic thing but at the same time it is thought to guarantee an eternal future because it stands as the enduring substrate through which individuals are guaranteed a life beyond finite, merely biological life. Therefore, nationalism, according to Cheah, is and can be a transcendental form of the limited intellectual and practical capabilities of the sensuous human creature. And it is because of this “transcending capacity” that nationalism—despite of its lack of philosophical grounding compared to religion, for instance, and of the doubt of many as to its capability to stand and last in this more globalized and connected world—survives and ‘the end of the era of nationalism,’ so long prophesized, to cite Anderson, is not remotely in sight. Today, as it was in the period when Anderson firstly published his widely cited book in the first half of 1980s, we still can see that nationalism is the most universally legitimate value in the modern political life.

One common issue in the topics of nationalism and the invention of nation that both Benedict Anderson and Pheng Cheah point, and which finds a fresh stress and perspective in the works of Henk Maier and James T. Siegel, is the process of “inventing and appropriating a national language.” By national language here I refer to the language that becomes the relatively exclusive mode of identification of a particular nation and that formally and legally solidifies it as a separated entity that is different from other nations. First of all, all four thinkers and writers mentioned above agree that the invention of the national language happens with or at the cost of the disappearance, death, and dissolve of

the truth language. What is the truth language? Anderson defines the truth language as the “single, privileged system of representation” (1991: 14-15) through which the ontological reality is apprehensible. The Latin of the Rome Catholic Church, the Arabic of the Koran, the Examination of the Chinese are only few examples of the old truth languages. Two basic features of the truth language—which sometimes is also called sacred language—are its perceived capability to explain human experience in totality and its tendency to embrace and convert people into it.⁸ The death of the truth language did not happen without reason. Anderson mentions that there are at least two reasons for the death of that vertical, hierarchical religious and sociospatial community of the truth language. The first reason, although sounds Eurocentric at first, is applicable to other cases of the truth languages. It is the expedition of European to the rest of the world—the departure, or the going out, from home—to see many more ways of living and ways of organizing society. Generally speaking, introduction to something new always challenges and reshapes one’s previous presuppositions and beliefs. This, as we have discussed in the previous chapters, happens to Minke, too, when he departs from his old, parental home to learn European modernity. He begins to see things from a new perspective. The Europeans who left their home countries to see, explore and later exploit the other parts of the world learned new things and new “truths” from the people of those parts of the world. With

⁸ This feature is what, according to Anderson, will differentiate the nation from the religion, because instead of taking in people into its embrace just like the sacred language of religions, national language becomes an instrument of a particular nation to exclude, exile, and contain others from joining a particular nation-state. National language, therefore, can function as an instrument to otherize others.

these, they challenged the only truth they grew up with. This may also suggest that the enterprise of colonialism is not a one-way traffic of influence. In the interaction between the colonizer and the colonized, however limited this could be, both find ways to influence each other.

Still according to Anderson, the other reason for the diminishing of the truth language is related to the development of print-capitalism. Indeed, modern printing has fundamentally changed the face of the world. It has democratized not only the knowledge but also the “power.” Books and printed materials have been for ages the source of knowledge, and of power, and since their numbers were very limited, they were very expensive and hard to get. Only the haves could afford them. In the past, these sources of knowledge and power had thus been the monopoly of a handful of the church clerics, the imams, and the aristocrats. But with the rapid development in mass printing technology they are now available to more of the common people. The consequence of it is that the old center cannot be held up anymore. Doors to knowledge, as well as to power, are open. Of course, we are not too naïve to ignore the other fact that print-capitalism has not only democratized many things but also has created a new elite class (bourgeoisie). Among these new elite groups, several of them would be nervous enough, and also brave enough, to lead others in the new paths. Minke, the pioneer of that new path in Indonesia, is always fascinated by the modern era. And among many achievements of the modern era, Minke “never stopped marveling ... printing” because “people can reproduce tens of thousands of copies of any photographs in just one day” so that “I could see for myself everything from

all over the world upon these printed sheets of paper” (Toer, 1990a: 17). Printing has indeed opened the door to modern world for many inhabitants of the earth. But printing, or what is being circulated through printing to be more precise, is never neutral as well. It carries a message and that message what makes it not innocence. In addition, printing facilities are owned by capitalists and regulated by states who want to make sure that their interests in one or another ways being satisfied.

The experience of losing the truth language is probably an inevitable thing, as today more and more people from different parts of the world meet and interacts to each other in an unprecedented level in this globalized world. It is just as we cannot stop the child from leaving their parents’ house and being mature and different. But this experience cannot be belittled as well. The loss of the truth language leaves a huge hollow space previously occupied by the relatively solid identity. This empty space needs to be filled with something else. So, just like the loss of the perceived union with “the mother” of the Lacanian Imaginary Order needs to be recuperated in the Symbolic Order with many *objet petit a*, big and small, and with the acquisition of language that will enable the child to communicate his or her needs to the outside world and to make sense of what happens in that outside world, so does the experience of the loss of the truth language. The loss of the truth or sacred language is recuperated by the acquisition of a vernacular. In nationalism setting, this vernacular—which is limited and far from being capable of explaining the human experience in its totality—is appropriated and promoted to the level of national language. These acts of acquisition and appropriation of the new national language simply

reconfirms the desire to make a break from “the mother’s truth language” from the parts of the newly born states. In many cases of the Asian, African, and Latin American postcolonial states, “the mother’s truth language” refers to the languages of the European and North American colonizers. The same acts can also be viewed as a sign of the birth of the subjectivity from the part of the new nation and a desire to create its own space, separated from the old space of the masters. The making of a vernacular into the national language further solidifies the separation of the new nation from its “cultural mother.”

About this, Pheng Cheah writes:

“The revivification of a vernacular national culture was as important to Fichte writing in Prussia where even in the time of Frederick the Great (who described German as a semibarbarous tongue), the social and aesthetic ideals and the *lingua franca* of the court were French, as it was to Kenyan novelist, Ngugi wa Thiong’o, who insisted on writing in Gikuyu in 1980s to reverse the linguistic and cultural alienation imposed by British colonial education policies and American neocolonial global culture” (Cheah, 2003: 5).

How postcolonial states chooses the vernacular—or the tongue—to be acquisitioned, appropriated, and promoted to the level of the national language is different from country to country. But, the will or the desire to break from the colonizer, the master, or “the mother” is always there to motivate the acts. Some new postcolonial states did not make as bold break as others from their European or American masters. Australia, as far as my knowledge, chooses to keep the language of their former colonizer, English, as their primary and first language. India and Malaysia still retain English as their second language after their own national languages, Hindi and Malaysian respectively. Indonesia is, on the

other hands, an example of a few new nations that make a bolder break with their former colonizers, at least superficially. Indonesian primary and secondary schools do not teach Dutch (and Japanese) to their students. Children from the age of six or seven are systematically taught and strongly encouraged to speak Indonesian in their daily activities, both inside and outside school. Old men and women still speaking Dutch or Japanese are seen as antique, another term for “odd.” They become laughing stocks for many people. Many will even see them as being unpatriotic. Moreover, Dutch and Japanese are not in the list of the most desirable foreign languages to learn by most Indonesian students. They will instead spend hours every week to study English and/or Mandarin, two world languages many teachers in Indonesia believe to be the most useful tools to navigate in this globalized world.

But, in my opinion, it is exactly in this regime’s attitude to systematically make Indonesian absolute where the problem lies. And it is also here where, I will argue, the critique that Pramoedya voices in his *Buru Quartet* locates. Indonesia, as we have discussed and as what Pramoedya seems to believe, is a postcolonial state that was invented through the process of imagining the future, through the admission of its hybridity and the ability to transcend that hybridity in order to invent its own unique space, and through the acceptance of its dynamic, non-essentialist, “on-going” characteristics. But with the rigid cooptation and standardization of Indonesian by the regimes, which, in its broader sense, can be read or understood as the enforcement of a single interpretation of what makes truly Indonesia, there is no more room for dynamics in the nation. Any effort

to make Indonesian absolute is a denial to the original spirit of Indonesia. Indonesian language, originally a vernacular—one of many hundreds we have in Indonesia—has been promoted to the height of the only language of truth in Indonesia at the cost of the dying of those many other tongues. The regime through its many bodies and agencies creates regulations about what is good and right in Indonesian language. And, the consequence of this is terrible: those who do not “speak” the same language, those who disobey the rule—in a broader sense, those who do not align themselves with the regime’s interpretation of truth and embrace it—must be “exiled,” just like Pramoedya Ananta Toer had experienced.

The many systemic and systematic efforts to make Indonesian “the truth language” signify how Indonesia as a postcolonial state, which declared its independence in 1945, is not as a real break from the colonialism as some might assume. There is something quite non-revolutionary in Indonesian revolution. James T. Siegel has for some times echoed his suspicion over this issue when he writes:

“It is well known that, despite attempts in another direction (to dream a new future), the Indonesian anticolonial revolution was not a social revolution. .. it meant that another hierarchy was established, one similar but not the same as the colonial version. What are the roots of this hierarchy? Is it the revival of regional, in particular, Javanese ideas? To some extent, indubitably. Is it an inheritance from the Dutch? It is clear that to some degree the forms of national authority in Indonesia today reproduce the colonial model” (1997: 6).

Indonesian nationalism is thus, we can say, a dream or a desire failed to keep. It is an act of imagining hard maintain. Indonesia, although originally conceived as a space where mongrelization and other dynamics of hybridity can freely float—where peoples from

different racial, religious, and social-economic backgrounds can interact with each other in significant ways and at the same time build one imagined community—has so far failed to keep its promise to the subjects. Viewed this way, Indonesian nationalism is more like a simple act of recuperation of what has lost, i.e. the stability of a “standard” identity, than a struggle to constantly keep up with the desire to create a just society, as Minke dreams, where everyone “becomes a free human being, not given orders, not giving orders” (Toer, 1990a: 128). Indonesian nationalism toppled down the European master to simply replace it with local bandits.

From his exile in Buru, Pramoedya lamented about this horrific situation: “[S]adly when Indonesian’s sovereignty was finally restored . . . , the event was followed not by social unification but by social caste-ification instead. National freedom had been achieved but not so the aspirations behind independence” (Toer, 1999: 252). Pramoedya saw that the situation in Indonesian postcolonial state, especially under Suharto, is not far better, if not worse, than the situation under Dutch colonialism when “Nationalist exiles [were] sent . . . to Digul, in the then Dutch New Guinea, and other parts of the country in 1930s” because these exiles were “. . . provided [with] financial support. But here [in Buru], in the middle of this fruitless savanna, we political prisoners were forced to survive by intuition” (Toer, 1999: 39). Comparing the atrocity of Suharto with the brutality during the Japanese occupation, Pramoedya, moreover, wrote: “The hunger that the political detainees endured behind Indonesian’s prison walls between 1965 and 1968 resulted in mortality rate even higher than was found in rural areas of the country between 1942 and 1945 when the

country was ruled by Japanese bayonets” (66). In short, “Death in Buru is commonplace” (84).

The awakening of Indonesian national consciousness can be seen as the raise of subjectivity—or, to follow Lacan, the dawn of Symbolic Order—of the colonized. And with this subjectivity comes the choice. The subjectivity from the part of the colonized in Indonesia is manifested, among others, in the choice to invent and promote Malay to the position of unifying language. Malay became the language with imaginary power that unites and mobilizes people vis-à-vis the others, which, in this case, the Dutch as the colonizer. Previously having been the lingua franca that enabled people from different parts of the Indonesian archipelago to communicate to each other and with foreign traders from Asia and Europe, which otherwise had not been possible, Malay rose to the position of a solid formal language. Seen from one perspective, this choice is a bold action, since Malay was not a tongue spoken by the majority who would then comprises Indonesia. People may ask: why Malay, why not Javanese, for example? While a conventional answer argues that Malay is lack of feudalistic aspects that is easily spotted in many other Indonesian vernaculars including Javanese and Sundanese and therefore is less threatening to the growth of democracy in the young nation, this choice reflects the bold dreams of the nation’s founding fathers and mothers of Indonesia to create an inclusive and dynamic state.

The choice of Malay also suggests how Indonesia as a state, just as its national language, is and should be seen as a project that is “under continuous construction.” Malay

was a very poor language when it was promoted to be Indonesian today. So is Indonesian today that is riddled by many borrowed words as it stammers to make sense. Indonesian is unstable. It constantly changes from time to time, not only in forms but also in the contents. It frustrates its speakers, just as being expressed by Agus R. Sarjono, an Indonesian poet and author:

“We know that KBBI (Indonesian Big Dictionary) is very thin (book). The thinness of that Indonesian Dictionary suggests the poverty of vocabulary of Indonesian language. Worse still, that thin and poor dictionary is also unstable. A thin dictionary is probably excusable. But an unstable dictionary is beyond forgiveness and frustrates those who may want to master Indonesian” (2011).⁹

What is unstableness in the language but a clear signage that that language is the language in the making? Henk Maier, the Professor of Literature of Southeast Asia and Indonesia at University of California, Riverside, very well acknowledges that nature of Indonesian when he writes:

“Malay ... was an open language with ... unfulfilled potential. It was the language of that was to be concretized in the future. ‘Indonesian’ was a project; it was function as the ‘national language’ somewhere in the distance, somewhere under the canopy of the sky, behind the creaking door, in a national culture that was equally under construction. ... The words [in Malay] have no reference or even meaning, so it seems; they could better be described in terms of sensations. They are again, invitations to make sense rather than to discover sense. ... As soon as we try to connect the images, construct a comprehensive signification and memorize

⁹ Originally an article entitled “Bahasa Yatim Piatu” (Orphan Language”) and is written in Indonesian “Kita tahu bahwa KBBI sangatlah tipis. Ketipisan kamus bahasa Indonesia menunjukkan miskinnya kosakata bahasa dalam bahasa Indonesia. Celakanya, kamus yang tipis dan miskin itu labil pula. Kamus yang tipis mungkin masih bisa dimaafkan. Namun kamus yang labil hampir tak termaafkan dan membuat frustrasi mereka yang ingin menguasai bahasa Indonesia.” (*Tempo*, June 6-11, 2011).

them, they escape us, and we are left with fragments and disjunctions again. We are pushed along in a river, so to speak, forced to move along with the telling, towards an unknown future, trying to create novelties in the process and yet keep some kind of memories, the basis of coherence and consistence” (2002: 75, 77).

It is precisely this unstable, poor, and stammered language that Indonesian postcolonial state, particularly under Suharto, tried so hard to establish as stable, rich, and powerful. But as Maier suggests, Indonesia itself is a state in the making. Understanding it the other way only means a denial to its very own nature.

Why, we might ask, is it very hard to maintain the aspiration behind Indonesian nationalism and why is Indonesian nationalism prone to be bent to another direction as suggested by Siegel? Part of the answer, I think, can be found in the “inherent nature” of postcolonial nationalism itself. In other words, the incapability of many postcolonial states to deliver their promises should not be a big surprise at all. Many thinkers have already talked about this. Frantz Fanon, for example, has for some times warned us against the pitfalls of (postcolonial) nationalism when he wrote in his now classic work, *The Wretched of the Earth*:

“History teaches us clearly that the battle against colonialism does not run straight away along the lines of nationalism. . . . National consciousness, instead of being the all-embracing crystallization of the innermost hopes of the whole people, instead of being the immediate and most obvious result of the mobilization of the

people, will be in any case only an empty shell, a crude and fragile travesty of what it might have been. ... This traditional weakness, which is almost congenital to the national consciousness of underdeveloped countries, is not solely the result of the mutilation of the colonized people by the colonial regime. It is also the result of the intellectual laziness of the national middle class, of its spiritual penury, and of the profoundly cosmopolitan mold that its mind is set in" (1963: 147-8).

Nationalism in many parts of Asia, Africa, and South America is, according to Fanon, a simple direct reaction toward colonialism, with no or very limited critical understanding of how it works and how this same mode of inhumane exploitation can simply be reproduced by different actors. Nationalism and national independence in these postcolonial states is no more than what he called neocolonialism, where "the national bourgeoisie will be quite content with the role of the Western bourgeoisie's business agent, and it will play its part without any complexes in a most dignified manner" (1963: 152-3). In other words, nationalism in those postcolonial states will simply become the echo of the Europe's voice, and never be a real voice itself, as being suggested by Jean-Paul Sartre in the introduction to Fanon's book:

"These walking lies (the national bourgeoisies) had nothing left to say to their brothers; they only echoed. From Paris, from London, from Amsterdam we would utter the words "Parthenon! Brotherhood!" and somewhere in Africa or Asia lips would open "...thenon! ...therhood!" (Fanon, 1963: 7).

Pheng Cheah, a more contemporary thinker and writer, is also aware of this potential danger in nationalism. But while admitting this possible pitfall of nationalism when he writes early on in his book, *Spectral Nationality*, that "the common association of

nationalism and the desire for the archaic suggests that nationalism destroys human life and whatever future we may have because its gaze is fixed on the frozen past” (2003: 1), Cheah also sees the possibility of nationalism as a way to transcend the finiteness of human’s life, to transcend the cultural homelessness resulted from the experience of loss of the old, stable identities. Nationalism, according to Pheng Cheah, is a part of culture in the broader sense that can become a space for human self-actualization. And, at the same time, Cheah admits how that culture, just like organism, is an integral part of vitalist ontology, suggesting the dynamic, organismic nature of culture—and of nationalism as well. It is in that fine balance of understanding the past and imagining the future where ideal nationalism should locate itself. Indonesian nationalism, so it seems, is still in struggle to even understand that balance. It may start with the right kicks: with a belief of sharing the same experience of loss, with a solidarity build upon the experience of suffering under the same colonialism, with a consciousness of its hybrid nature, and with a common desire to imagine a better, more just, and inclusive society where people from different races, religions, and all walks of life may come and significantly talk to each other and not merely speak. But then, it fell in the old trappings of nationalism: the reestablishment of the old system of exploitation with a different actor.

The reading of the Buru Quartet suggests that Indonesia can potentially be a great nation if it does not shut down its own potentials as a revolutionary and imagined community. If Indonesia keeps open itself for the dynamics of its hybrid society, it could be a beautiful haven for many who can contribute significantly for the common good and

at the same time retain their uniqueness. And as it is an imagined community, all the subjects must be patient that these all are the ideals. The best is that they can be as close as can be to them.

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